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**Environmental monitoring of refugee camps using
high-resolution satellite images**

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Improve existing and develop new
products and methods**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports on the results of the ENVIREF WP3000: *Improve existing and develop new products and methods*. The objective of this WP was *to improve existing and develop new methods and procedures to fill the gap between customer requirements and traditional EO products used by the relief-community*. Major relief organisations requirements for geographic information was investigated and documented under WP2000: *Identify Customer Requirements* [Enviref, 1999].

From these user requirements the work has focused on retrieval of information on infrastructure, water resources, vegetation cover, and elevation from satellite data in areas occupied by refugees. The results of the analysis are presented as spacemaps at scales ranging from 1:250,000 up to more than 1:10,000.

Satellite imagery of various types have been acquired and analysed for three different study areas, including several refugee camp settlements in

- 1) The Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia border region in Europe,
- 2) The southeastern part of Nepal in Asia,
- 3) The eastern part of Kenya in Africa,

Each study area represents different climatic, environmental and refugee related conditions.

Satellite sensors with spatial resolution ranging from 6 to 30m, including LANDSAT TM/ETM+, SPOT, and IRS-1D have been used for retrieval of *infrastructure, water resources and vegetation cover* which are presented in maps with scale ranging from 1:15.000 to 1:250.000. Images from all these sensors were used to accurately measure the location and extent of a refugee camp. The spatial resolution of these images is not good enough to reveal any details within a camp area, e.g. to identify independent buildings, tents, roads, and so forth.

Water bodies derived from LANDSAT and SPOT XS images have been combined with digital elevation data in order to determine the river flow direction. Such information is important both in terms of management of water for drinking supply and drainage of wastewater, but also for preserving the camp from flood and erosion in more tropical areas. Multi-temporal satellite acquisitions have been used to map changes in the watercourse several lakes in Nepal.

Vegetation cover mapping has been performed on satellite data alone, and by use of additional non-satellite information such as vegetation cover maps. Without any supporting information about the vegetation in an area, e.g. from field observations or available vegetation maps, only very general maps can be made, such as location and distribution of forest. These maps can on the other hand be prepared very quickly, and also be used to plan where *in situ* measurements should be performed. With additional information about the vegetation more detailed maps can be prepared, showing e.g. the distribution of the various vegetation types.

While the medium-high resolution satellite images are useful for general mapping of environmental conditions and large-scale infrastructure, the detailed structures of refugee camps can only be studied by very-high resolution images which traditionally only have been

available from aerial surveys. During the study we have been able to acquire and analyse 1m resolution images from the IKONOS satellite to perform mapping of details such as roads, footpaths, separate buildings, tents, and water sites inside the refugee camp area. This is the first satellite to deliver very-high resolution satellite imagery on the commercial market. An especially important result of the IKONOS-data analysis is the potential for identifying single tents and buildings inside a camp area. For the investigated camp settlement in Nepal close to 100% of all present tents and buildings were identified and could be counted in the image. This information can be used to make better estimates of the number of people living in a camp, which is needed to determine the amount of food, medicine and other supplies for the camp. IKONOS images also have the potential to be used for detailed planning of refugee camps, including expansions, and assessments of environmental changes in the immediate surroundings.

The study shows that by providing fast access to general thematic information over a larger region the LANDSAT-7 ETM+ sensor could be a valuable data source for the relief community, also due to both the global data archive and the low price of only USD600 per image. For performing more detailed analysis, which is especially needed at a later stage during a crisis situation, images at a resolution available e.g. from the IKONOS sensor is needed.

The results of the data analysis and products derived from satellite data will be evaluated by a group of end-users from different humanitarian relief organisations at a workshop to be hosted by UNHCR in January 2001. The outcome of this workshop will be used in the overall assessment of the project results.

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1 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION OF THE SATELLITES USED

1.1 BACKGROUND

Common high-resolution earth observation satellites operate either in the optical (i.e. 0.3-14 μ m wavelength) or the microwave portion of the spectrum (i.e. 1mm-1m wavelength).

The term optical is used because lenses and mirrors can be used to refract and reflect the observed energy, basically it is a combination of sun light reflected at the earth's surface and radiance from the earth that is observed by the optical sensors (i.e. visible to thermal range). This means that these sensors only can operate during sunlight, and that e.g. clouds, shadows and haze will obscure the signal received. This means that sometimes a combination of several images must be produced in order to obtain a useful view over a larger area or region. Use of multi-spectral sensors that register in different parts of the optical spectrum is particularly valuable for discriminating different features on the ground, as the difference in the spectral signature curves for e.g. soil and vegetation varies as a function of the wavelength.

High-resolution microwave radar sensors emit and receive their own energy and can thus operate independent of daylight. These sensors are also capable of penetrating the atmosphere under virtually all conditions. Depending on the wavelength used the radar waves can penetrate clouds, haze, shadows, light rain- and snowfall, and smoke. On the other hand microwave reflections bear no direct relationship to their counterparts in the visible and thermal range, and surfaces that may appear rough in the visible range may be seen as smooth by the radar sensor. The images produced can appear quite different from 'normal' views, and thus require a completely different interpretation approach.

1.2 LANDSAT TM/ETM+

The American LANDSAT programme started with the launch of the LANDSAT-1 satellite in 1972. This was the first unarmed satellite specifically designed to acquire data about earth resources on a systematic, repetitive, medium resolution, multi-spectral basis. The 3 first satellites in this series carried the Multi-Spectral Scanner (MSS) system, which had 4 bands ranging from 0.5-1.1 μ m and a ground resolution of 79m. The LANDSAT-4 satellite launched in 1992 was equipped with the technically improved Thematic Mapper (TM) sensor. The TM-sensor contained 7 different bands and had a ground resolution of 30m (including a thermal infrared band with 120m resolution). With the 1999 launch of LANDSAT-7 also a panchromatic band with 15m ground-resolution became available in addition to the TM-sensor. Simultaneously a very user-friendly price policy was introduced, with only USD 600 per scene stored in the USGS archive. The LANDSAT 7 Mission Objective is to provide timely, high quality visible and infrared images of all landmass and near coastal areas on the Earth, continually refreshing an existing LANDSAT database. Data input into the system will be sufficiently consistent with the current data in the database in terms of acquisition geometry, calibration, coverage, and spectral characteristics to allow comparison for global and regional change detection and characterisation. The LANDSAT-7 project will continue to make LANDSAT data available for U.S. civil, national security, and private sector use as well as academic, foreign, and commercial uses. Another goal of the project is to expand the uses of such data. LANDSAT-7 is to have a design lifetime of five years. Simultaneous acquisition of panchromatic and multi-spectral data is mandatory. Both LANDSAT-5 and LANDSAT-7 are active today. The swathwidth of a TM scene is 185km.

Band	Sensitivity [μm]	Resolution [m]
1	0.45-0.52 (blue)	30
2	0.52-0.60 (green)	30
3	0.63-0.69 (red)	30
4	0.76-0.90 (near-infrared)	30
5	1.55-1.75 (mid-infrared)	30
6	10.4-12.5 (thermal-infrared)	120/60 ¹
7	2.08-2.35 (mid-infrared)	30
8	0.52-0.90 (panchromatic)	15

¹60m with the ETM+ sensor

Table 1.1. Characteristics of the LANDSAT TM/ETM+ sensor

1.3 SPOT

The French SPOT (Système Pour l'Observation de la Terre) programme started in January 1991 (also Sweden and Belgium participate in this programme). Four satellites have been launched so far, and today both SPOT-2 SPOT-4 are active. The special rotating viewing capacity of the sensor ($\pm 27^\circ$ off-nadir) makes it possible to obtain stereo-pairs from adjacent orbits, which can be used to construct digital elevation models (DEM). The swathwidth of a scene will increase with increasing incidence angles, i.e. ranging from 60 to 80km. Simultaneous acquisition of panchromatic and multi-spectral data is possible under certain conditions. An improved SPOT-5 is scheduled for launch late 2001, and will provide panchromatic images at 5 and 2.5m resolution in addition to three multi-spectral bands with 10m resolution.

Band	Sensitivity [μm]	Resolution [m]
1	0.50-0.59 (green)	20
2	0.61-0.68 (red)	20
3	0.79-0.89 (near-infrared)	20
4	1.58-1.75 (shortwave infrared) ¹	20
Pan	0.51-0.73 (SPOT1-3) 0.61-0.68 (SPOT-4)	10

¹SPOT-4 only

Table 1.2. Characteristics of the SPOT sensor

1.4 IRS-1C/D

IRS-1C/D is the second generation (increased spatial resolution) of the Indian Resources Satellite programme that started with IRS-1A in 1988. IRS-1C started acquiring data in January 1996, and was followed by IRS-1D in October 1997. Both satellites are still active. The satellites carry a panchromatic camera that can be steered up to $\pm 26^\circ$ off-nadir, thus allowing for a shorter revisiting time (5 days only at Equator). Simultaneous acquisition of panchromatic and multi-spectral data is not possible. The swathwidth of a panchromatic scene is 63-70km and 127/141km for a multi-spectral scene.

Band	Sensitivity [μm]	Resolution [m]
1	0.5-0.75 (panchromatic)	5.8
2	0.52-0.59 (green)	23
3	0.62-0.68 (red)	23
4	0.77-0.86 (near-infrared)	23
5	1.55-1.75 (shortwave-infrared)	70 ¹

¹141km swathwidth

Table 1.3. *Characteristics of the IRS-1C/D sensor*

1.5 IKONOS

IKONOS is the first Very High-Resolution (VHR) satellite available on the commercial market and started providing data in January 2000. IKONOS has the possibility to acquire data at up to $\pm 45^\circ$ off-nadir. This makes it possible to acquire stereo-pair images that can be used to construct digital elevation models (DEM), and to cover large areas during the same over-flight, including to some extent acquisitions along a direction oblique to the satellite ground track. Use of varying incidence angles also reduces the repeat cycle to only 3 days. It is possible with simultaneous acquisition, and the swathwidth of a full scene is 11km (smaller coverage can also be obtained).

Band	Sensitivity [μm]	Resolution [m]
1	0.45-0.52 (blue)	4
2	0.52-0.60 (green)	4
3	0.62-0.69 (red)	4
4	0.76-0.90 (near-infrared)	4
Pan	0.45-0.90	1

Table 1.4. *Characteristics of the IKONOS sensor*

1.6 ERS-1/2

In July 1997 the European Space Agency (ESA) launched ERS-1 satellite which among others carried a Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) sensor operating in the C-band (5.6cm wavelength). This was followed by the launch of ERS-2 in 1995. Although the highest resolution available in ERS SAR images is $4*20\text{m}$, the most frequent resolution used is $25*25\text{m}$, though this cannot be compared to what can be seen in optical images with the same resolution due to the distinct different measurement techniques used. The swathwidth of a scene is 100km. During the so-called tandem period only one day separated subsequent acquisitions of the same ground area by the two sensors, which allowed for a unique opportunity to produce digital elevation models using the interferometry technique.

2 PROCESSING STEPS, METHODS AND PRODUCTS

2.1 GEOMETRIC CORRECTION

The intent of geometric is to compensate for distortions in the image caused by e.g. variations in altitude, attitude and velocity of the sensor platform, and panoramic distortion, earth curvature, atmospheric refraction, and relief displacements, so that the image can be treated as map. Systematic distortions are easily corrected once known, and are usually handled by the data providers. Random distortions are corrected by analysing well-distributed ground control points, i.e. features of known ground location (preferably in 3D) that can be

accurately located in the image. The later process includes transforming the image to a known map-projection, e.g. the UTM-system. The relation between a pixel in the distorted image and the geometrically correct map co-ordinates are determined by a least-mean-square regression analysis. Through the re-sampling process the pixel value to fill in at the right place in the output image is determined, where basically three different methods are most commonly used, all having their advantages and disadvantages. The more sophisticated the method the more ground control points are needed.

The corner co-ordinates of the satellite image (in 2D) are usually supplied together with the image, and this is in general enough to obtain a decent relative correction, though this is not enough to correct for local distortions e.g. caused by high relief within the imaged area. More co-ordinates are needed for comparing the image with available vector data of e.g. infrastructure and rivers in a GIS (the accuracy depends on the image resolution and scale of the vector data). Available vector data can in most cases be used to verify and eventually improve the relative positioning, and thereby obtaining an absolute position of the satellite image. For detailed studies an accurate measurements of lengths and areas though, digital elevation data preferably at a scale close to or better than the image resolution must be used for the geometric correction.

2.2 IMAGE PROCESSING

Several methods for enhancing certain features in the image exist, including stretching the image contrast, combining different bands of multi-spectral data into false colour images, and applying spatial filters for e.g. removing noise or enhance linear structures in the image. Especially in when producing false colour images the image can appear quite different from a 'natural' view, and can thus be difficult to understand for none-experts.

For the ENVIREF project the main challenge is to produce satellite image maps with colours that appear as natural looking as possible for none-experts (i.e. comparable to an overview of the ground as seen from an aeroplane). Thus whenever applicable a natural colour look have been attempted by using a RGB-combination with data registered in the blue spectrum in the blue channel, green in the green, and red in the red. This is possible with both LANDSAT and IKONOS data. For SPOT though, which does not register data in the blue spectrum, green was used for the blue channel, a combination of green and near-infrared in the green, and red in the red channel. This produces an image with green vegetation, while water appears with a violent tone and some man-made features such as roads and buildings also appear with green tone.

An interesting possibility when both high-resolution panchromatic data and lower resolution multi-spectral data exist over the same area is to merge them using e.g. the so-called RGB→HIS→RGB transformation, available e.g. in the ERMAPPER software package. The method will generate a colour image with the same resolution as the panchromatic image, and has been applied to the IKONOS images, the LANDSAT-7 ETM+ image, and a combination of the LANDSAT-5 TM and the IRS-1D images. It should be noted that this method only is intended for visual presentation and interpretation of the data, as the spectral information in image will be altered. In short, the method is three-folded. First an RGB-image of the multi-spectral is prepared. This image is then transformed to the IHS-space (Intensity, Hue, and Saturation), another method for presenting colours. Here, the intensity channel is replaced by the high-resolution panchromatic image. The altered HIS-image is then transformed back to the RGB-space. Contrast and colour adjustments might be needed in order to obtain an

esthetical and interpretable final result. The whole process is shown schematically for an IKONOS image in Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2.

Merging Ikonos images process

Figure 2.1. Example of the processing steps for the IKONOS images

Merging Ikonos images

Figure 2.2. Improving the resolution of the IKONOS data by merging through the RGB→IHS→RGB transformation.

2.3 INFRASTRUCTURE MAPPING

Knowing the infrastructure is a key issue for all relief operation planning. Such information can be derived at a larger overview level using images from LANDSAT ETM+ (i.e. the panchromatic band), SPOT and IRS-1C/D, and at a smaller detailed level using images acquired by IKONOS, e.g. within the camp area. At the same time, the overview information is needed at an earlier stage than the more detailed information thus both types of data might be needed, especially during longer-lasting operations.

Even if the roads are smaller than the spatial resolution of the satellite sensors they can often be seen clearly in the image due to their linear structure and high contrast against their surroundings. Edge and line filters may enhance the roads further. The curvature of man-made roads makes them separable from natural features such as smaller rivers. Parts of the road can be 'lost' in the image, e.g. due to clouds, forest and low contrast against the surrounding vegetation thereby qualified guessing is sometimes needed during the interpretation. Without field-verification or other information it will most certain not be possible to determine whether a part of a road gets 'lost' in the image due to the above mentioned causes or because it has been damaged. At the same time it will most often not be possible to determine the sate and type of roads seen, especially when using the coarser resolution images.

Even if it is easy to extract objects such as buildings from the satellite images, it is impossible to state whether the buildings are e.g. schools or medical centres. Information from people working in the camp is important for the final result and also for acceptance of the product.

The mapping was done by applying various filters, and then by onscreen digitising of the features interpreted as roads and airfields. In addition to what was believed to be the major roads in a region only the roads leading directly to the camp was digitised, in order to enhance only the information most important for planning a relief operation. The vectors representing roads where assigned a red colour in order to be easily identifiable in the map.

2.4 VEGETATION MAPPING

2.4.1 BACKGROUND; VEGETATION MAPPING AND SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING

Vegetation interferes with sunlight in several ways. Especially in areas of high vegetation density the leaf is the most characteristic and influential component of this interference.

A plant leaf (see Figure 2.3) is a highly specialised structure adapted to photosynthetic activity. It consists mainly of four different layers, an upper and lower epidermis, a layer of elongated parenchymatic cells and a layer of spongy mesophyllic cells. Especially in the latter layer large air filled volumes predominate between cells. The epidermis, with its stomatal cells, secures gas exchange (CO_2 , O_2) and is largely transparent to incident **Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; 0.4-0.7 μm)**. The chloroplasts in the parenchyma cells do the solar energy absorption, while the hydrated mesophyll cells contribute water to photosynthesis.

The function (photosynthesis) and structure of the leaf generate a special spectral signature, as illustrated in Figure 2.3. From this figure it is possible to recognise three main regions of hemispherical reflectance

Figure 2.3. *Left) Schematic cross section of typical citrus leaf (after Harris 1987)*
Right) Leaf and soil hemispherical reflectance (after Tucker and Sellers 1986)

1. In the region of PAR (sub-regions a-c) the leaf absorption is very high, due to the pigments of chlorophyll a and b, and the carotenoids in the chloroplasts. The Red wavelengths (0,62-0,70 μm) usually stand in the strongest contrast to soil reflection due to high chlorophyll absorption. Another factor increasing the pigment absorption is the high scatter¹ of the PAR, giving pigments multiple chances to absorb the active wavelengths.
2. Between 0,74-1,1 μm , in the near-IR region, the reflectance is very high. Thus absorption is minimal, and scattering amplifies the spectral reflectance, especially for dense canopies. The sub-region from 0,79-0,90 μm is considered most appropriate for monitoring vegetation because it avoids atmospheric water vapour absorption. The reflectance can reach fifty per cent on the 'IR plateau', the level of which depends on the internal structure of the leaf. The level increases with the number of layers of cells, their size and the orientation of cell walls (Guyot, G and Riou, J 1988).
3. In the region of 1.3-2.5 μm , mid-IR there is high absorption due to the liquid water of the mesophyll cells.

As seen from Figure 2.3, soil reflectance increases steadily over visible and near-IR wavelengths; and in the mid-IR wavelengths it oscillates like, but above, reflectance from vegetation. Potentially the best regions to obtain vegetation information separately from background information are thus the Red and the near-IR (0,79-0,90 μm) which are closely connected to chlorophyll density and green leaf density respectively (Tucker, CJ and Sellers, PJ, 1986). A multi-spectral, optical satellite image is usually displayed as a false colour composite of three layers: a blue, green and red layer. The IR channel is normally displayed in the red layer, and the Red channel in the green; and this combination of high values in the red layer and low values in the green layer gives vegetation a red colour.

The hemispherical reflectance of leaves is not, however, the only factor influencing the vegetation canopy reflectance. Colwell, JE (1974) mentions several other parameters which

¹High scatter is due mainly to differences in the refractive index between the air spaces (1.0), hydrated cells (1.4), and the irregular facets of the exteriors of cells.

can change vegetation canopy reflectance even if the leaf hemispherical reflectance remains constant, or vice versa.

- Leaf hemispherical transmittance
- Leaf area and orientation
- Hemispherical reflectance and transmittance of supporting structures (stalk, trunks, limbs, petioles)
- Effective background reflectance
- Angular effects; e.g. topography, shadowing etc.
- Pixel size

These parameters are important at different levels and to a varying extent. Nevertheless, most methods for monitoring vegetation are based upon the characteristic differences between the leaf hemispherical reflectance of the visible and IR region. The Red and IR bands do often contain more than 90% of the vegetation information in a multispectral image (as referred in Bannari, 1995). Plotting the Red – IR data-space for a vegetated surface draws a characteristic feature, commonly known as the ‘tasseled cap’. This is illustrated in Figure 2.4, and the outlined feature is explained by the high IR DNs accompanying the low Red DNs. The different mathematical combinations between these channels are called vegetation indices and they represent quantitative measurements indicating the vigour of vegetation. In addition to amplify the vegetation characteristics, vegetation indices also normalise data and thus reduce topographical effects; and also the amount of data is reduced to one dimension only.

Figure 2.4. *The tasseled cap*

Several authors sum up the different indices that are in use (Bannari, A, *et al.* 1995, Estes, JE and Cosentino, MJ 1989, Olsson, K 1985, Perry Jr., CR and Lautenschlager, LF 1984, Tucker, CJ 1979) and Perry Jr., CR and Lautenschlager, LF (1984) mention 48 different versions of vegetation indices. Vegetation indices have also been classified in different ways. One classification type can be made on the grounds of the interpretation of the index/ the operation used to derive it (difference, ratio or orthogonalisation), Bannari *et al.* (1995), however, suggest to classify them according to their history of development. They mention

two stages; a first developmental stage based solely on linear combinations or raw satellite digital numbers, and a second conceptual stage based on the knowledge of the physical phenomena that influences the monitoring of the vegetation and their interactions with each other and the vegetation. The Normalised Difference Vegetation Index ($NDVI = (NIR - Red)/(NIR + Red)$) is a widely applied index. The success of this index resides in the normalisation it permits (Bannari et al.).

2.4.2 CLASSIFICATION

Classification of digital imagery consists of recognition of features and patterns and their assignment to classes. These classes can be statistical clusters or specified land-cover classes. Both spectral and spatial patterns are of interest. The approach can be either manual or digital/automatic.

The visual/manual technique uses the skills of the human brain to recognise patterns in the image and the interpretation gives us information of the spatial distribution of features described by the sum of pixels. The interpretation done by the human brain is based not only on the pattern of features but also on factors such as shape, size, shadow, tone/color, texture and site (Lillesand and Kiefer 1994). Some of these factors can be limited by the ground resolution of the satellite. Borry *et al.* (1990) (as referred in Holmgren, P and Thuresson, T 1998) describes manual interpretation of forest type to be more reliable than digital/automatic classification. Roy, PS, *et al.* (1985) emphasis that visual interpretation is a subjective method and hence mapping borders will vary between interpreters. However, this is of limited importance for broad scale studies. For detailed mapping they suggest computer-aided techniques. On the other hand, a manual approach for broad scale studies of sufficiently large areas is very cumbersome, time-, and labour- consuming.

Visual interpretation is not only applied alone but also as part of digital approaches, e.g. as in the segmentation and the following evaluation of the defined segments (Burger, H, *et al.* 1997). Woodcock, CE, *et al.* (1994) uses manual techniques to label clusters derived from a complex classification.

Digital classification methods normally use statistical or spectral decision rules to assign the unit considered to different classes. The unit considered can be either a single pixel or a region. As opposed to the per-pixel approach a region-based classification first requires segmentation, i.e. a clustering of spatially and spectrally similar pixels. In the current study the per-pixel approach was applied.

The classification algorithms are executed on the images themselves or on partly processed images, for example a segmented image. However, the classification principles are the same if one deals with segment- or per-pixel- classification. Classification is a two-step process

1. The training stage
2. The classification stage

The training stage

Training is the process of defining the criteria of which the patterns are recognised (Hord, 1982, as referred in (ERDAS imagine 8.3). The training can be either unsupervised or supervised.

Unsupervised training or clustering is a more computer-automated process that basically recognises spectral clusters defined on a solely statistical basis. Different clustering methods exists; among them ISODATA (Iterative Self Organizing Data Analysis) clustering and the RGB clustering.

The first iteration of the ISODATA clustering determines the means of the maximum number of clusters (set by the user) arbitrarily. The spectral distance between all the pixels and the cluster means are calculated and the candidate pixel is assigned to the spectral closest cluster. When all the pixels are assigned to a cluster the means are recalculated and used for defining clusters in the next iteration. The process continues until a user-specified portion of the pixels, set by the convergence threshold, does not change from one cluster to another between two iterations. The user also sets the maximum number of iterations and clusters to be processed.

Good a-priori knowledge of the area is not required. However, the clustering will turn out useless if no appropriate interpretation of the clusters is given. Normally this approach requires additional information to interpret the classes generated and a post-classification to merge or split classes.

Supervised training is a method in which the user defines a set of classes of interest. The user selects the signatures for these classes; i.e. the user supervises the computer in the training process. This requires some a-priori knowledge about the area and the spatial distribution of these reference/ground truth data. The resulting classification is usually very dependent on the quality and quantity of reference data. Mayer, KE and Fox, L (1981) attributes the high accuracy for certain variables to the large amounts of training data, and the low accuracy for other variables to insufficient training data.

It is recommended sampling between $10n$ and $100n$ pixels per class, n being the number of channels or bands used in the classification. It is also recommended to take several smaller homogeneous than fewer larger samples (Swain and Davis, 1978 and Campbell, 1981 as referred in San Miguel Ayanz, J and Biging, GS 1996).

The result of the training process is a set of signatures for the classes selected or recognised, e.g. mean value and variance. These signatures can be either parametric or non-parametric.

Parametric signatures describe the pixels in the training sample by a set of statistical parameters. These parameters are the input to a statistical based classification.

A non-parametric signature is delimited by boundaries in a feature space/scatter diagram rather than described by statistical parameters. However, it is possible to calculate statistics for one type of feature space objects; i.e. the ellipse which fulfils the normal distribution requirements of a parametric classifier.

The most crucial part of the training step is the evaluation of the signatures. Are the signatures overlapping? If that is the case the spectral information of the data itself cannot support the classes of interest. This is often one of the main problems with a per-pixel classification that only uses the spectral information content of the image.

For unsupervised classification two results are generated: a set of signatures and a completely classified dataset. Hence, signatures from an unsupervised classification/training can be input to a supervised classification. The signatures created by the training stage are the input to the classification stage. Pixels and/or regions are then assigned to classes based on a decision rule. Different decision rules exist:

- Minimum distance
- Mahalanobis distance
- Maximum likelihood
- Parallelepiped/feature space classification

2.4.3 UNSUPERVISED CLASSIFICATION OF THE NDVI

In emergency situations it is normally not time to get hold of high quality reference data for the area of interest. The advantage of using a vegetation index is then, that it automatically reflects certain aspects of the vegetation, i.e. its vigour. It is therefore possible to state some general points about the vegetation in the area studied, however, the vigour may be the same for different types of vegetation. In order to recognise the different types of vegetation it is pre-requisite with additional information.

The NDVI is derived based on channel 4 (Near-IR) and channel 3 (Red), see flowchart in Figure 2.5. The subsequent unsupervised classification is performed using the software ERDAS/Imagine and the ISODATA clustering algorithm (Erdas field guide, 4th edition). Fifteen classes were selected for the classification and the convergence threshold was set to 95%. The advantage of classifying the NDVI compared to a simple slicing is that the derived classes reflect statistical clusters in the dataset.

Agricultural areas are visually easy to recognise by their pattern and heterogeneity. For all the areas the main agricultural activity is concentrated on the plains. These plains were delimited by digitising using the distribution of agricultural areas and the height contours as guidelines for its extent. Within each area of interest polygons delimiting the sloping areas were also digitised.

The merged classification result was vectorised using the *ArcView* software package. Vegetation polygons (dense and open) within the different topographical polygons were selected, thus giving a total of four classes. The total image processing is visualised by the flowchart, see Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5. Flow chart for the processing of the vegetation maps prepared for the Kosovo border region.

2.5 WATER RESOURCE MAPPING USING REMOTE SENSING

2.5.1 INTRODUCTION

Remote sensing in hydrogeology and hydrology is used mainly to suggest favourable areas for development in terms of the relative amount of water available and the spatial characteristics that might condition development (Jakson *et al.* 1983). The most important applications of remote sensing in hydrology and water quantity management include

- horizontal distribution of precipitation
- soil moisture
- groundwater exploration
- evapotranspiration
- distribution of snow and ice
- surface water
- basin characteristics

2.5.2 DRAINAGE BASIN ANALYSIS

Generally, a *drainage basin* is defined as the total land surface occupied by a branched network of stream channels, bounded by a drainage divide or watershed (Strahler and Strahler 1989). Hydrologically, it is the entire area providing runoff to and sustaining a part or all of the streamflow of the main stream and its tributaries. The importance of studying the drainage basin emerges from the following:

- 1) Some of the drainage basin parameters may be an important guide to how a basin will function hydrologically (Dingam 1978 in (Ritter *et al.* 1995))
- 2) They may predict a catchment's hydrological response to rainfall.
- 3) They may distinguish one catchment from another for comparative or classification purposes.

Studying a drainage basin and the related analyse began with the ideas of James Hutton whose law was expressed by Playfair in 1802 (Gregory and Walling 1976). During the nineteenth century, quantitative measures were proposed for specific areas or for particular problems; but by the early twentieth century, methods for ordering stream were being conceived. In 1932, R. E. Horton made a great step forward by consolidating pervious work, adding new measures and proposing general methods for the description of drainage basin characteristics. These characteristics include morphological, soil, geological or structural, and vegetational factors. Horton proposed rules for how each factor could be expressed in a way relevant to the function of the drainage basin. Many of these ideas and methods were later developed in the hydrological context.

Drainage Basin Parameters

Several physical variables control the location and amount of water that infiltrates through the surface and recharges the underlying aquifer. Among the more important surface expressions are catchment area, stream intensity, drainage density and catchment slope.

Catchment area

Catchment area is one of the more important details in the description of basins since it influence the water yield, and the number and size of the streams. It includes all the upstream land and water surface area that drain into a specific location on the stream. It can be the catchment area for whole stream system, or the catchment area for a particular point on a stream. The area is delimited by the so-called *topographic divide*, a theoretical line that passes through the highest points between the stream system and its neighbours. In the case of topographical maps catchment boundaries are located by using the contour lines. These can be supplemented using stereo pairs of aerial photographs. Boundaries can be drawn by following the tops of the ridges. A catchment area can be measured directly from maps using a planimeter or a digitiser with appropriate software.

Drainage density

Drainage density is the ratio of the total length of all channel segments for all orders (for definition see next section) within a basin to the total basin area. It can be determined by the formula:

$$D = \sum_{j=1}^K \sum_{i=1}^N L_{ij} / A$$

where D is drainage density, K is the highest stream order, A is the basin area, N is the number of segments and L is the length of those segments. The result of the formula gives the average length of channels per unit area and as such reflects the spacing of the drainage ways. Drainage density is directly controlled by the interaction between geology and climate; and because these two factors differ from region to region, wide variations in drainage density can be expected. In general, resistant surface materials or those with high infiltration capacities have widely spaced channels and consequently lower drainage densities. As the resistance or the surface permeability decreases, runoff is usually removed in a greater number of closely spaced channels, and the drainage density tends to be much higher. In general, high drainage density is associated with areas covered by rocks of low permeability that provides conditions suitable for appreciable runoff over the basins. Low drainage density is favoured in regions with subsoil materials of low permeability and where relief is low and conditions favourable for downward infiltration.

Stream frequency

Stream frequency is the total number of all stream segments per unit area and can be expressed as

$$F = \sum_{j=1}^K N_j / A$$

where F is the stream frequency, K is the highest stream order, A is the basin area and N is number of segments.

Basins that have high stream frequency values tend to collect more runoff water, which then may increase the flow and discharge out of the basin. In such basins the rate of the downward infiltration is low. On the other hand, basins that have low stream frequencies have less opportunity to collect surface runoff. Consequently, the rate of flow and discharge out of the basin is low. This gives a great chance for downward infiltration.

Mean catchment slope

The slope of the catchment will influence the velocity of surface runoff water and its infiltration. Van Haveren (1986) gives several definition of the mean basin slope (S_b), e.g. computed as:

$$(S_b) = \frac{(\text{Elevation at } 0.85L) - (\text{Elevation at } 0.10L)}{0.75L}$$

where L is the maximum length of the basin, i.e. $0.10L$ near the lower part of the catchment, and $0.85L$ towards the upper end.

Mapping of Drainage Patterns

Topographic maps and field surveys have traditionally been used for mapping drainage patterns, the former by tracing the watercourse shown as blue lines on the maps. Morisawa (1957) compared and evaluated drainage patterns obtained from both types of sources. She showed that the disadvantage of the blue line method is that not all streams may be represented on the map, and that contour crenulations may indicate where a valley is present although a blue line may not occur in the base of the valley indicated. Therefore drainage patterns should be constructed by first tracing the net of the blue lines and then supplementing this net by additional segments according to the patterns of the contour crenulation. This method depends chiefly on the standard of precision and accuracy adopted during the production of the topographic maps as well as on the scale and contour intervals of the map. Now days aerial-photograph and satellite images has been widely used for mapping drainage network (Babiker, 1999) and (Kock1993) (Smith19##). The method used is digitising the drainage network from simple enhanced images or by extracting them from DEM.

Lineament analysis

Mapping of linear features on remote sensing data has been an integral part of many groundwater exploration programmes in hard rock terrain. Many workers have investigated lineament data with respect to their groundwater potential, several with an emphasis on arid or semi-arid hard rock areas (Krishnamurthy, *et al.* 1996), (Kock 1993), (Sander *et al.* 1997) and (Smith, *et al.* 1997).

Lineament features play very important role in groundwater recharge and flow in hard rock terrains. This depends on their distribution, orientation and density. A *lineament* is defined as a mapable, simple or composite linear feature of a surface whose parts are aligned in a rectilinear or slightly curvilinear relationship and which differs from the patterns of adjacent features and presumably reflects a subsurface phenomenon.

A lineament may be classified as a continuous or discontinuous feature, depending on whether it consists of uninterrupted linear features or a series of closely spaced and aligned segments. Some lineaments (simple lineaments) consist of single types of surface features, for instance, straight drainage segments or a series of aligned cliffs, whereas others (composite lineaments) are made up of a combination of different geomorphic and/or tonal features such as straight drainage segments aligned with a nearby ridge segment.

2.5.3 SURFACE WATER

The surface water regime in an area can be expressed by the relationship between the four factors precipitation, surface flow, evapotranspiration and infiltration. Surface water becomes a potential resource only when it appears as rivers or in lakes. Aside from losses by evapotranspiration and infiltration, the flow through a channel or entering a lake depends on the upstream catchment area together with the amount of precipitation. The quality of the water, in terms of sediment load, depends mainly on the slope density in the catchment area and the density of vegetation that binds soil.

The monthly, daily and extreme precipitation can be estimated by using measurements of cloud-top reflectance and temperature on Meteorological-Satellite images as a gauge of the likelihood of rain falling, and by the use of multitemporal images showing snow cover and snow-melt rates. There are many remote sensing possibilities covering this part, including ground base radar, visible and thermal infrared satellite imagery, and microwave satellite. Evapotranspiration rates can be estimated from surface temperature average from metsats, and by models based on vegetation density derived from the use of very near-infrared and red reflectance contrast on multispectral imagery. Infiltration is a thornier problem and discussed later under the groundwater section. Catchment area and slope estimation, together with analysis of drainage networks, can be derived from Digital Elevation Models (DTM). Combined with estimates of the vegetation cover derived from remote sensing imagery each catchment can then be assessed qualitatively for likely levels of turbidity due to soil erosion.

The main input to studies of surface water as a resource focuses on the location and evaluation of sites for capturing flow and harvesting it for drinking water, irrigation or hydropower generation. Whereas long earth barrages can be used to pond water in broad valleys in gently undulating terrain, the best sites are where valleys narrow as they pass through more resistant rocks. Such thresholds are often floored by only thin mantles of permeable alluvium, and the construction of dams or barrages is aided by the small volumes required and firm footings. Thresholds are easily located on stereoscopic aerial photograph or satellite images.

2.5.4 GROUNDWATER

Satellite data has been used in exploration of groundwater for nearly two decades, beginning with LANDSAT MSS and then followed by the technically and spatially improved TM data. These were complemented first by SPOT multispectral (XS), panchromatic (P) including stereo pairs, and then by merging of radar and optical imagery. Even though remote sensing has evolved very rapidly, this does not mean that the earlier tools have been superseded. Satellite images have not replaced aerial photographs, SPOT has not rendered Landsat obsolete, and ERS1 will not replace SPOT. Rather the trend is towards a better distribution of technical tasks and a better adaptation of tools to find correct answers (Dutartre *et al.* 1993).

There are basically two approaches when using remote sensing in groundwater exploration. The first is generally applied to carbonate and basement aquifers, where fracture flow is the characteristic mode for water movement. Thus linear features in the image correspond to fractures that can imply an occurrence of groundwater. Well-sites often show a positive correlation with linear features or with the intersection between two features (i.e. features that can be fractures).

Figure 2.6. *Different types of ground water occurrence and well-sites*

The second approach is applicable to all reservoirs, and involves integrating remote sensing data with other sources of information to create hydrological thematic maps for water resources assessment.

Many features that could favour the occurrence of groundwater are visible on satellite data, especially in areas with limited regolith cover, types of rocks fracture zones, drainage pattern, various types of unconsolidated deposits, vegetation, etc.

The processes involved in using satellite data in prospecting for groundwater are mapping the above mentioned features, analysing them, and then identifying areas with favourable condition for groundwater availability.

2.5.5 GROUNDWATER INDICATORS

Using remote sensing in groundwater exploration is one of its most complex uses. The complexity results from the fact that the object of study, groundwater, is not portrayed directly on the data. Most applications of remotely sensed data, however, deal with surface phenomena, because it is the surface that is being photographed or imaged by satellite or aircraft. The subsurface hydrological conditions can be inferred from surface indicators, such as distributed geological features and structures, vegetation, streamflow characteristics, soil and soil moisture anomalies, vegetation types and distribution, discontinuity of ice cover on streams, different snow melting, springs etc. All these features can usually be identified in remote sensing images. The identification depends on the spatial and spectral resolution of the data as well as the size of the feature. Some of these features can be identified using standard processed false colour images. And other even relatively simple, digital image enhancement techniques can make significant improvements for the identification of the sought features. Gustafsson (1993) called these features collectively *groundwater indicators*.

The steps involved in using these indicators are:

- detecting the indicator from original or manipulated images.
- mapping
- analysis

The analysis varies depending on the procedures used. E.g. lineaments analysis reveals the location, concentration, length and orientation of the indicator. Many have used lineaments extracted from different types of remote sensing imagery as groundwater indicators. E.g. Koch (1993) in Red Sea Hills Sudan using large format camera, Gustafsson, (1993) in SE Botswana using Spot, (Krishnamurthy *et al.* 1996) in Tiruchirappalli district in India, using images from the Indian Remote Sensing Satellite, (Mabee *et al.* 1994) on Georgetown Island in the USA, using a variety of aerial platforms and (Salman 1983) around Qena Province, Egypt, using Landsat (MSS).

Drainage network analysis includes pattern analysis that usually give an indication of the structure and composition of rocks, or drainage basin analysis that has a direct relation to the hydrologic behaviour of basins. Drainage networks can be treated in two ways:

- 1) to study its pattern in order to examine the degree of the structural control upon the drainage network (Kock 1993) or
- 2) to analyse the drainage network in order to determine e.g., its drainage density and drainage frequency and to relate these to hydrological behaviour (Smith *et al.* 1997).

The second approach mainly depends on the image resolution. The value of the drainage density can therefore be different for the same area if satellite images of different resolutions are used (Babiker, 1999).

The above mentioned indicators are the most commonly used indicators in exploration for groundwater using remote sensing data. They are usually supplemented by ground data (e.g. geophysical data or site location of wells) and different maps (e.g. geological or elevation maps) and then analysed them together in a GIS (geographical information system).

Hydrogeological studies can be considered in terms of a regional survey concerned mainly with understanding the general groundwater conditions of large area, or local surveys where the objective is determine a good location for a borehole or dug well. Alternatively a study may take a hierarchical approach, where the regional survey precedes the local survey. However, remote sensing will form only one element of any hydrogeological study and must be integrated with other phases of work.

When selecting image acquisitions care should be taken for seasonal variations. Some knowledge about the area or region to be investigated is crucial for performing a good interpretation. Winter images at low sun elevation serve to emphasise structures and geomorphology as well as areas of sustained near-surface moisture, whereas summer and wet-seasons images often reveal more about the vegetation patterns and lithologies. Other imagery types have more specific applications. Thermal infrared (IR) can e.g. be used to extract information about the sub-surface moisture and perched water tables at shallow depth.

The use of remote sensing in hydrology is growing important mainly because of several unique aspects of the technique. Remote sensing imagery provides measurements of continuously data as opposed to the local point information that is obtained in the field. Further, remote sensing techniques can assess the state of the Earth's surface over large areas. Finally, remote-sensing techniques, especially those, which utilised satellite sensors, can be utilised to assemble long-term data sets. Furthermore, although the expenses associated with remote sensing imagery may seem to be high at first glance, upon close inspection, the cost is rather low compared to acquiring the same spatial information using conventional methods such as field surveys and to some extent aerial photographs.

2.5.6 MAPPING CRITERIA

A lineament usually represent joints, zones of joint concentration, dikes, dike swarms, faults or shear zones. Thus lineaments can be zones either of weakness or of resistance in the crust, which have been etched out or sculptured by agents of erosion. Both types of lineament can be distinguished on satellite images and aerial photographs depending on their resolution and scale. Kock (1993) classified lineaments into: lineaments depicting topographically low zones of less resistant rocks called “negative lineaments”, and those which stand out topographically as zones of more resistant rock termed “positive lineaments”.

Some lineaments clearly visible on satellite images are often not recognisable in the field. This is because they either correspond to wide strips of more highly fractured rock and/or they do not show any displacement along their fracture planes and thus show no lithologic or structural contrast on either side of the plane, which indicates the existence of a fractured zone.

The best recognisable structural features on space images are vertical fracture zones corresponding to simple extension fractures, normal faults, transcurrent faults or strike slip faults. Thrust faults with relatively low-angle planes and curved traces are more difficult to detect because they have usually been less well enhanced by erosion.

Horizontal extension fractures usually play a secondary role in regulating groundwater flow. They are generally formed near the surface due to stress release during the removal of the lithologic overburden. These exfoliation structures do not penetrate the crust very deeply and are basically irrelevant in terms of regional groundwater circulation. In contrast, open fractures or fractures filled with coarse rock fragments represent potential infiltration sites for rainfall and runoff as well as being excellent water transmitters.

All the factors mentioned above have direct implications for the process of mapping lineaments and need to be considered when interpreting the resulting mapped data.

Mapping procedure

Using the mapping criteria outlined above, the lineaments are mapped in satellite images through the following steps:

1- Image rectification and restoration

Raw digital images usually contain geometric distortions so significant that they cannot be used as maps. The sources of these distortions range from variation in the altitude, attitude and velocity of the sensor platform to factors such as panoramic distortion, earth curvature, atmospheric refraction, relief displacement and nonlinearities in the sweep of a sensor. The intent of geometric correction is to compensate for the distortions introduced by these factors so that the corrected image will have the geometric integrity of a map. The distorted image is corrected by analysing well-distributed ground control points (GCPs) occurring in the image. As with their counterparts on aerial photographs and maps, GCPs are features with known ground location that can be accurately located on the digital imagery

2- Image enhancement

Procedures are applied to image data in order to more effectively display or record the data for subsequent visual interpretation. Normally, image enhancement involves techniques for increasing the visual distinctions between features in a scene. The objective is to create

“new” image from the original image data in order to increase the amount of information that can be visually interpreted from the data. There are no simple rules for producing the single best image for a particular application. Often several enhancements made from the same raw image are necessary.

2.6 USE OF ERS SAR INTERFEROMETRY FOR PRODUCING DTMS

The method of interferometry tries to find a point in common to the two input images so that an interferogram with good correlation may be generated around that point and height information can be obtained from these data. After several steps the height information is extracted and a file containing heights (DEM) is produced. The method basically consists of the following steps:

- Image registering
- Geometric Correction
- Generation of an Interferogram
- Unwrapping phase
- Final DEM Production

Complex SAR images (i.e. containing both an amplitude A and a phase θ , expressed as $A \cdot \exp(j\theta)$) from e.g. the ERS-1/2 satellites covering roughly the same area are used as input data. An interferogram is produced using the phase from the two different data acquisitions, where changes in the phase at the same point can be used to compute the height. The area covered by each image is 100x100km, and the pixel-size is 20m in the along-track direction and 4m in the across-track direction. Small differences in the acquisition point are required, ideally about 100m, for calculating the phase-difference. During the so-called tandem-period ERS-1 and ERS-2 acquired data over approximately the same area on the ground with only 24hours difference (followed the same theoretical orbit). Images taken within a short time interval reduce the potential for differences caused by changes on the ground that can influence on the interferogram, e.g. different atmospheric conditions.

When a good point in common to both input images has been **registered** an interferogram is generated. An **interferogram** consists of a set of two images (Coherence and Phase). A bright Coherence image is a sign of good correlation, and the Phase image shows the slope and contains height information.

The Phase is a function of the heights on the ground. Another step called **Unwrap** is needed to extract the real height from the phase by means of some numerical algorithms. This also requires knowledge of some fixed height-points within the area covered by the image.

Before generating the final product, **geometric correction** must be done: the geometry of the image obtained by one of the two satellites is corrected and the image taken by the other satellite is re-positioned knowing the distance between the two sensors (baseline).

The output image is a DEM containing height data and it has been projected to UTM WGS84 projection. Geometric correction and projection steps can be performed just after the registration or nearly at the end just before the **production of the DEM**.

The method can be successful under certain conditions:

- Areas where the topography is not too uneven or too steep (i.e. less than the satellite incidence-angle of 23°)
- Areas without much vegetation (especially forest)
- Good GCPs and reference cartography

This means that the technique is ideal for barren and level areas such as deserts, arid land, and glaciers.

Figure 2.7. Flowchart for the processing of DTM from ERS SAR interferograms

1: INPUT DATA

2: REGISTER + INTERFEROGRAM

3: OUTPUT

Figure 2.8. *Example of the interferometric processing.*

3 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Reflecting the investigated satellites' spatial resolution and ground coverage the developed products have been divided into four *product-levels* where each level can have up to four *product themes*. The product theme will be produced at the appropriate level depending on the situation and available data sources.

Level	Name	Scale range [1:]	Appropriate satellite
1	Overview	200,000-50,000	LANDSAT
2	Camp location and surroundings	50,000-20,000	LANDSAT/SPOT/IRS
3	Camp overview	20,000-10,000	IRS/IKONOS
4	Detailed camp infrastructure	>10,000	IKONOS

Table 3.1. *Product level*

Level	Name
1	Infrastructure
2	Vegetation
3	Water resources
4	Elevation

Table 3.2. *Product theme*

The analysis has been carried out for three different locations, representing various climate and natural environments. The Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia border region is a part of the Mediterranean climate belt, an area rich in terms of bio-diversity, but is at the same time hampered by rapid increasing development and industrialisation, often at the expense of local environmental conditions. The area investigated in Nepal represents a semi-tropical, heavy cultivated area, in danger of erosion due to among others deforestation and improper cultivation, while the camps in Kenya represents a semi-arid area with relatively fragile natural resources and low rates of biomass growth.

4 KOSOVO

4.1 BACKGROUND

As a consequence of the war activities in the Kosovo-region spring 1999 several refugee camps were established in Albania and Macedonia for Kosovo-albanians that had to leave their country. Our study area concerned altogether 12 camps at 5 different locations, i.e. the refugee settlements Bojane, Neprosteno, Senokos and Radusa in Macedonia and seven camps around Kukes in Albania. The western part of the region is very hilly, and includes a.o. a large mountain massif separating Albania from Kosovo and Macedonia. The Albanian region is dominated by mining industry, and contains mainly forest and more or less abandoned agricultural fields in addition to some villages and smaller settlements. The Macedonia region constitutes mainly of a very large agricultural area in addition to several villages and settlements of various sizes. Satellite data acquired for the study area includes a LANDSAT-5 from September 1997, and IRS1-D panchromatic scene from May 27 1999, 3 ERS SAR PRI scenes from respectively August 4 1997, May 31 1999 and August 9 1999, as well as 26 ERS SAR SLC-images from the ERS1-2 tandem period for producing a Digital Elevation Model of the region using the interferometry technique. The satellite data coverage is shown in Figure 4.1. In addition we received from UNHCR and USAID vector data of roads, rivers, lakes, borders, cities/villages and geographic places, including some tabular information, at a scale of 1:200,000 and 1:1,000,000. This data served as the background for the image georectification. We also received several forest maps of Albania prepared by the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) of the UN, Italy.

More information about the Kosovo-refugee programme can e.g. be found at:
<http://www.unhcr.ch/world/euro/se0/kosovo.htm>

Figure 4.1. *Satellite data coverage for the Kosovo-border region case study. The coverage of the ER-SAR images obtained is very similar to the IRS-1D coverage.*

4.2 USE OF LANDSAT TM

Initially, a free low-resolution (pixel-size about 250m) version of a LANDSAT-5 scene of September 1997 was downloaded from Eurimage's Internet site. This image was geocorrected by NERSC and Satellus, and overlaid vector data received from UNHCR and USAID. Approximately 40 hardcopies of this space map were distributed to relief agencies operating in the crisis region. The distributed hardcopy measured 70x90 cm (A1 format), and had a scale of 1:250,000. GPS co-ordinates of camp locations were acquired in field and submitted to ENVIREF by UNHCR. Several problems were encountered during the production of the small-scale space map. As this was an archive image it was assumed to be readily available. However, it took unforeseen much time until the image was in house. In order to disseminate a space map to the relief community while the situation in Kosovo still was in an emergency phase, a temporary solution by producing a space map from the freely low-resolution LANDSAT image was decided upon. The space map was sent out in hardcopy format with express mail services on May 10 1999, two and a half weeks after the final product should have been available according to the initial plan.

A full-resolution version of the Landsat TM scene was received in early October 1999, and rectified using the IRS-1D scene (accuracy ± 1 pixel). Figure 4.2 below is a small, degraded improved version of the *Overview* space map. When producing the new version of the space-map comments and critics from the user group and other relief organisations that received the original map was taken into account.

Figure 4.2. Overview map (improved version)

4.3 USE OF IRS-1 D

The *Camp location and surroundings* maps were made using the panchromatic IRS-1D image (6m resolution). For some areas also in combination with the LANDSAT TM image (30m resolution) using a RGB→IHS→RGB transformation and thereby obtaining a colour-image with the same level of detail as in the greyscale IRS-1D image. For the less vegetated areas (i.e. in Kukes/Albania) this transformation gave a reasonable colour impression while for the agricultural fields in Macedonia natural colours were not obtained. Presumably this is mainly due to that the images were obtained at different seasons. Each map covers about 10*10km. Five different camp areas were mapped at this level, see Figure 4.3 to Figure 4.7. The Cegrane camp area could not be mapped due to the cloud coverage.

The *Camp overview* maps were made using the IRS-1D panchromatic image of May 27 1999. Each map covers about 1.3*1.3km, with a scale close to the limit of the image resolution. The limitations of the low radiometric resolution of the IRS-1D sensor become especially evident for the actual camp areas, which only appears as white regions without any details.

4.3.1 CAMP LOCATION AND SURROUNDINGS

Kukes - Albania
Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure

Figure 4.3. Camp location and surroundings map for the Kukes region, Albania.

Neprosteno - F.Y.R. Macedonia Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure

Figure 4.4. Camp location and surroundings map for the Neprosteno region, Macedonia.

Bojane - FYR Macedonia Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure

Figure 4.5. Camp location and surroundings map for the Bojane region, Macedonia.

Radusa - FYR Macedonia Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure

Figure 4.6. Camp location and surroundings map for the Radusa region, Macedonia.

Senokos - FYR Macedonia Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure

Figure 4.7. Camp location and surroundings map for the Senokos region, Macedonia

4.3.2 CAMP OVERVIEW MAPS

Figure 4.8. *The Tree camp at Kukes, Albania*

Figure 4.9. *The Bashkia (north) and Kukes II (south) camps at Kukes, Albania.*

Kukes - Albania

Figure 4.10. The Kukes I camp at Kukes, Albania.

Kukes - Albania

Figure 4.11. The UAE (north), Cap Anamur (middle) and UNHCR/MSF camps at Kukes, Albania.

Neprosteno camp - FYR Macedonia

Figure 4.12. The Neprosteno camp, FYR Macedonia.

Figure 4.13. *The Bojane camp, FYR Macedonia*

Radusa - FYR Macedonia

Figure 4.14. The Radusa camp, FYR Macedonia

Figure 4.15. *The Senokos camp, FYR Macedonia.*

4.4 VEGETATION COVER MAPPING

4.4.1 BACKGROUND

The data set applied in the study is a LANDSAT TM image from September 1997, and two different classification approaches were tested. Before further processing the image was corrected for haze (Lillesand and Kiefer, 1994) and for geometric distortion. The geometric correction is a linear rectification with nearest neighbour re-sampling, using ground control points from the IRS-1D image of May 27 1999. The output resolution is 25 m, the projection is UTM zone 34 and the datum is WGS84.

Unsupervised classification of the NDVI

Initial only data on infrastructure (cities, roads, rivers, railway etc) and a very general set of height contours (500m interval) were available over the Kosovo border region.

The NDVI (Normalised Difference Vegetation Index) is derived based on channel 4 (Near-IR) and channel 3 (Red). The subsequent unsupervised classification is performed using the software ERDAS/Imagine and the ISODATA clustering algorithm (ERDAS field guide, 4th edition). Fifteen classes were selected for the classification and the convergence threshold was set to 95 %. The advantage of classifying the NDVI compared to a simple slicing is that the derived classes reflect statistical clusters in the data set.

There are three main areas of interest in the current case study; the camps in the Kukes area, in the Cegrane and Senokos area and in the Neprosteno area. The regions of interest were studied and for each area classes were merged to reflect two broad classes of vegetation; open and dense vegetation. This merging was based on a visual inspection of the classification compared to the original multi-spectral image.

Agricultural areas are visually easy to recognise by their pattern and heterogeneity. For all the areas the main agricultural activity is concentrated on the plains. These plains were delimited by digitising using the distribution of agricultural areas and the height contours as guidelines for its extent. Within each area of interest polygons delimiting the sloping areas were also digitised.

The merged classification result was vectorised in using the software package *ArcView*. Vegetation polygons (dense and open) within the different topographical polygons were selected, thus giving a total of four classes.

Supervised classification of the 6 band data set

The 6 band TM dataset (channel 6, thermal band is not included) is basis for the supervised classification. For this classification a forest – land-cover paper-map from Albania is used as reference data. The map is made by FAO – GIS (1995) and is in the scale 1:200 000. The map is based on the interpretation of multi-temporal LANDSAT TM satellite images and KFA 1000 space photographs. The forest types are described using the existing Albania forest map as ancillary data. Classes on this map are given in Table 4.1.

Class	Description	Groups	
1	Urban areas		
2a	Intensive agriculture (mainly in flat areas)	Agriculture areas and fruit trees	
2b	Agriculture in sloping areas (small agricultural field/fruit trees mixed with abandoned land, grassland and shrubbery)		
2c	Pastures and related grassland	Grasslands and unproductive lands	
2d	Highly dissected and eroded land/ river banks		
3a	“Garrigue” (low scrubs/ bare rocks)	Scrub or degenerate forests	
3b	Mediterranean “Maquis”		
3c	High scrubs ~ Mediterranean “Maquis” or Quercus sp., Fraxinus sp.		
3d	High scrubs/ degenerate forest Quercus sp. Fraxinus sp, Acer sp.		
3e	High scrubs/ degenerate forest Fagus sp.		
4	Forest Poplar	Forest	
5	Forest Quercus sp., Fraxinus sp., Acer sp or Castanea sp.		
6	Forest Fagus		
7	Forest Pinus sp., Abies sp.		
7a	Open forest Pinus sp., Abies sp.		
8	Forest Pinus heldreichii christ		
8a	Open forest Pinus heldreichii christ		
9	Swampy areas		Water bodies and related vegetation
10	Water bodies		

Table 4.1 Legend of the Albania forest – land-cover map used as reference data set

Signatures for the classification scheme was selected based on this map. However, due to difference in scale and in geometry the possibility to locate reference areas for all classes was limited. The selection of classes and their reference areas is an iterative process. Several classifications were performed before the final classification scheme was selected. The decision was based on a visual comparison of the classified image, the paper-map and an evaluation of the signatures selected. The final set of signatures selected is seen in Table 4.2.

Class number according to Albania map	Description
1	Urban
2_1	Agriculture1
2_2	Agriculture2
2d	highly dissected and eroded land / river banks
2d	highly dissected 2
2c	pastures and related grassland
3a	Garrigue
3d/3e	High shrub, degenerate forest
5	Quercus
6	Fagus
7/8	coniferous forest
9	swampy area
10a	shallow water
10b	water/sea
10c	Lake
10	Water
11.	dense vegetation
12	Shadow
13	Clouds

Table 4.2. The final set of signatures selected

The signatures were evaluated by calculating a contingency matrix using the maximum likelihood decision rule, which is the same rule as applied in the classification itself. The contingency matrix is seen in Table 4.3. It shows the classification result of the signatures themselves and the result is given in percentage of the total number of pixels in each class.

Data	10a	10b	10c	2d	2d	3a	2c	13	9	10d
10a	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10b	0.00	99.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.55
10c	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2d	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2d	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
3a	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2c	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	99.78	0.00	0.00
9	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00
10d	0.00	0.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	99.45
12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
7/8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
3d/3e	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2_1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2_2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.22	0.00	0.00
Column Total	500	1868	907	65	122	65	194	2233	547	548

Data	12	7/8	3d/3e	2_1	2_2	6	5	11	1	Row Total
10a	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	500
10b	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1864
10c	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	907
2d	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	65
2d	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	122
3a	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	65
2c	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	194
13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2228
9	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	547
10d	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	552
12	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	172
7/8	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	316
3d/3e	0.00	0.00	96.41	0.00	1.25	0.46	1.44	0.00	0.00	466
2_1	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	50
2_2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	91.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	73
6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	99.26	0.00	0.00	0.00	1075
5	0.00	0.00	3.59	0.00	7.50	0.28	98.56	0.00	0.00	232
11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	106
1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	72
Column Total	172	316	474	50	80	1083	209	106	67	9606

Table 4.3. Contingency matrix for alb_ref4.sig - maximum likelihood decision rule

The maximum likelihood classifier applies a parametric decision rule. In essence this method delineates ellipsoidal “equiprobability contours” in the scatter diagram (Lillesand and Kiefer, 1994) and assigns the candidate pixel to the class it most probably belongs to. The mean plot for the selected signatures over the six bands (all bands except band 6) is seen in Figure 4.16.

Figure 4.16. The mean of selected signatures over the six bands used for the supervised classification.

4.4.2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Unsupervised classification of the NDVI

The fifteen classes resulting from the unsupervised classification is described in more detail in Table 4.4, which also shows the generalisation of the classes and the final classes selected.

Class	Description	Generalisation		Comment
1	Water and dark shadows	Non-vegetation		These areas are represented by the natural colour composite on the final product
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7	Open vegetation/ soil	Non-veg.	Open veg.	Included in “open vegetation” for the Kukes area
8	Open vegetation	Open vegetation		This class is used in the topographic selection
9				
10				
11				
12	Dense vegetation	Dense vegetation		This class is used in the topographic selection
13				
14				
15				

Table 4.4. Classes resulting from the unsupervised classification

The topographic selection gives a total of four main classes of vegetation:

- Open vegetation in sloping/ mountainous areas
- Dense vegetation in sloping/ mountainous areas
- Open vegetation on cultivated plains
- Dense vegetation on cultivated plains

The final products show these classes overlaid on a natural colour composite of the TM image; Blue channel (TM1) displayed in the blue layer, green channel (TM2) displayed in green layer and red channel (TM3) displayed in red layer.

This method generates a product with a very general information content on vegetation. The main advantage is that you don't need a high quality reference dataset to generate this product, which in most cases will be lacking due to tight time-restrictions. When the generated classes are generalised to only two broad classes of information it is also a very high reliability within these two classes. It is possible to increase the number of classes by assigning reasonable land-cover types based on a visual interpretation done by an image analyst expert. However, the more informative such a map gives an impression to be the less is the reliability compared to a more general map. Normally it is recommended that the accuracy of the classification is assessed (Congalton, RG 1991). However, an accuracy assessment requires reference data, which in this case study wasn't available.

Supervised classification of the 6 band data set

The final, merged classes of the classified image are listed in Table 4.5. . The maps are shown as overlays of the classified image and layers of roads, railways, camps, cities and the 500 m contours.

Class	Description	Comments
3d/3e	High shrub, degenerate forest	
6	Forest – Fagus sp.	
5	Forest – Quercus sp., Fraxinus sp., Acer sp., or Castanea sp.	
7/8	Forest coniferous	
-	Deciduous forest/ open vegetation	“Dense vegetation” in slopes in Macedonia, no reference data
1/2	Urban/ Highly dissected and eroded land/ river banks	Spectral similarities
2_1	Agriculture1	
2_2	Agriculture2	Mainly in Macedonia, less intensive and mixed units.
10	Water	Merged from 10a, 10b, 10c and 10d
	Shadow	
9	Swampy area	
2d	Highly dissected and eroded land/ riverbanks	Merged from 2d_1 and 2d_2
3a	Garrigue	
2c	Pastures and related grassland	
	Clouds	

Table 4.5. Final classes in the classified image, after merging

As seen in Table 4.3 the separability of the signatures selected are very good; more than 90 % of the pixels of within all the signatures are classified to its right class. However, it should be noted that this only suggests that the signatures, based on the current selection of pixels, are most similar to themselves than to any other signatures. This does not tell anything about the

accuracy of the classification itself. The question to be raised is whether the selected reference area for the different classes is a representative selection throughout the dataset. One main problem in this study is the scale of the paper map used as reference data. The scale and resolution is smaller than allowed by the potential of the TM image, and even if an area is assigned to a specific class it is likely that it is actually a mixture of several land-cover types, dominated by one type. Another problem with the available reference dataset is that there is a spatial inconsistency between the reference-system for that map and for our image; i.e. the same coordinate on both datasets does not refer to the same location on the earth surface. The projection of the two datasets are the same (UTM), however, the datum is not specified on the paper map. Other reasons to the geographic incompatibility can be that our imagery has the highest accuracy in the area of interest, which only partly is within the Albania. Errors are likely to increase as we moves away from our area of interest.

Due to these two factors, it was only possible to locate relatively large areas of homogenous land-cover on the TM image; i.e. homogenous on the paper map. One big area of reference data is not necessarily representative throughout the image. In the process of selecting signatures this was recognise as a problem. This was especially true for agricultural areas. They came out well in the coastal area of Albania, but were completely lacking in the plains in Macedonia. Agricultural areas are difficult to classify because they are very heterogeneous both in size and in actual land-cover, i.e. land-cover differ even if the land-use is the same. Some areas might be barren, others densely vegetated and in addition there are infinitely many stages between these to extremes. Visually, however, it is, due to the same reasons, easy to recognise agricultural areas. It was easy, therefore, to pick new signatures in the Macedonian area. However, this introduced another confusion between these agricultural areas and the densely vegetated slopes in the geographical vicinity. Another signature was therefore selected, labelled "dense vegetation". No reference data exists for this class since it is selected outside the Albanian borders. Based on general knowledge about vegetation signatures it is likely that it could be deciduous forest or highly vigorous open vegetation.

Kukës, Vegetation map

LEGEND

<p>0 0.5 1 1.5 2 Kilometers</p> <p>0 0.4 0.8 1.2 Miles</p> <p>Datum: WGS84 Projection: UTM</p>	<p> Camp</p> <p> Town</p> <p> Major roads</p> <p>Contour lines</p> <p>500 m</p> <p>1000 m</p> <p>1500 m</p> <p>2000 m</p> <p>2500 m</p>	<p> Dense vegetation / forest in mountain-slopes</p> <p> Open vegetation in mountains/slopes</p> <p> Dense vegetation in plains dominated by agriculture</p> <p> Open vegetation in plains dominated by agriculture</p> <p>Image</p> <p>TM-Image; Blue channel, Green channel, Red channel</p> <p> Soil</p> <p> Settlement</p> <p> Shallow water</p> <p> Water</p>	
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Satellite image: Landsat TM acquired Sep. 1997 copyright (c) Eurimage 1998
GIS data provided by USAID, Refugee camp location provided by UNHCR

Vegetation map produced by:
Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), 1999
under ENVREF (NERSC, Satellus, Intocarto, UNHCR)

Figure 4.17. Coarse vegetation cover map for the Kukës region, Albania.

Vegetation map, Neprosteno

LEGEND

0 0.4 0.8 1.2 Kilometers

0 0.3 0.6 0.9 Miles

Datum: WGS84
Projection: UTM

- Camp
- Major roads
- Image
- Soil
- Settlement
- Dense vegetation / forest in mountain-slopes
- Open vegetation in mountains/slopes
- Dense vegetation in plains dominated by agriculture
- Open vegetation in plains dominated by agriculture

Satellite image: Landsat TM acquired Sep. 1997 copyright (c) Eurimage 1998
GIS data provided by USAID, Refugee camp location provided by UNHCR

Vegetation map produced by:
Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), 1999
under ENVREF (NERSC, Satelitus, Infocart, UNHCR)

Figure 4.18. Coarse vegetation cover map for the Neprosteno camp area, FYR Macedonia.

Vegetation map, Senokos and Cegrane

LEGEND

0 0.5 1 1.5 2 Kilometers

0 0.4 0.8 1.2 1.6 Miles

Datum: WGS84
Projection: UTM

ENVIREF

Camp

Town

Major roads

Railway

Contour lines

Dense vegetation / forest in mountain-slopes

Open vegetation in mountains/slopes

Dense vegetation in plains dominated by agriculture

Open vegetation in plains dominated by agriculture

Image

TM-Image; Blue channel, Green channel, Red channel

Soil

Mountain

Settlement

Satellite image: Landsat TM acquired Sep. 1997
copyright (c) Eurimage 1998
GIS data provided by USAID
Refugee camp location provided by UNHCR

Vegetation map produced by:
Nansen Environmental and
Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), 1998
under ENVREF (NERSC, Sateluis, Infocarto,
UNHCR)

Figure 4.19. Coarse vegetation cover map for the Senokos camp area FYR Macedonia.

Kukës, Vegetation map

Figure 4.20. Detailed vegetation cover map for the Kukës region, Albania.

Vegetation map, Neprosteno

Figure 4.21. Detailed vegetation cover map for the Neprosteno camp area, FYR Macedonia

Vegetation map, Senokos and Cegrane

LEGEND

0 0.5 1 1.5 2 Kilometers

0 0.4 0.8 1.2 1.6 Miles

Datum: WGS84
Projection: UTM

Camp

Town

Major roads

Railway

Contour lines

Dense vegetation / forest
in mountain-slopes

Open vegetation in
mountain-slopes

Dense vegetation in plains
dominated by agriculture

Open vegetation in plains
dominated by agriculture

Image

TM-image; Blue channel,
Green channel, Red channel

Soil

Mountain

Settlement

Satellite image: Landsat TM acquired Sep. 1997
copyright (c) Eurimage 1998
GIS data provided by USAID
Refugee camp location provided by UNHCR

Vegetation map produced by:
Nansen Environmental and
Remote Sensing Center (NERSC), 1999
under ENVREF (NERSC, Satelius, Intocarto,
UNHCR)

Figure 4.22. Detailed vegetation cover map for the Senokos camp area, FYR Macedonia.

4.5 WATER RESOURCES MAPPING

4.5.1 BACKGROUND

The area under investigation is rich in surface water, and is covered by number of rivers and lakes. Albania is traversed by a hydrographical network with a total length of more than 49,000km, and a mean density of 1.7 km/km². The annual volume of the water quantity of the rivers amounts to 41.2 km³. The area is also rich in terms of groundwater availability and big krastic springs, mineral springs and thermomineral springs. Thus, there seems to be no problems in terms of water availability for this region. The only problem might be water pollution. The main sources of water pollution are human settlement, industry and agricultural. A significant degree of pollution may enter through the river networks. Measuring of water quality and eventual pollution requires intensive field measurements, and is not really possible from the satellite sensors operating today.

Available data were a LANDSAT TM image, an IRS-1D image, a low-resolution digital elevation model (available for the whole world, free of charge from the USGS, with a horizontal resolution of approximately 1*1km and vertical resolution from 100-500m) and major rivers, roads and villages as coarse vector data (1:200,000 – 1:1,000,000). The LANDSAT TM image acquired in September 1997 was used to map the surface water in the region. Band 1,2 and 3 (i.e. the visual range of the spectrum) has been manipulated by simple image processing in order to highlight the surface water. The drainage network and the boundaries of the catchment (water divide) of the area were mapped by creating vector layers (themes) on the top of the image, and using the digitising function (using the mouse for drawing). Also other methods subtracting water bodies were examined, e.g. automatic classification and scattergrams (i.e. spectral signature in band *i* vs. spectral signature in band *j*). Both methods were good in highlighting large water bodies such as larger lakes and wide/long rivers, but failed in terms of smaller lakes and rivers. Automatic classification is technically time consuming compared to other methods, especially the raster to vector conversion, and the need for erasing the classes that do not represent water bodies. Thus, there is no single method that can be generally used for extracting water resources from remote sensing imagery.

The flow direction for the rivers was determined by superimposing the river-vectors on top of a coarse DTM that was available for the region. The DTM was also been used for improving the borders of various catchment areas that was mapped. In dryer regions this is very important information when planning for e.g. water storage.

4.5.2 RESULTS AND COMMENTS

By looking at the map shown in Figure 4.23 the following comments can be made:

- A small part of the area drain to the Danube River, the rest drain to the Adriatic Sea.
- The main water divides in the area flow along the high ridges between Kosovo-Macedonia, and Macedonia-Albania.
- Most of the towns and refugee camps were located in flat areas less 500m above the sea level, beside rivers or lakes.
- Water availability is not a significant problem in the investigates area

4.6 USE OF ERS SAR FOR CAMP IDENTIFICATION

During the Kosovo-crisis we experienced how fragile the optical satellite system can be. When up-to-date geographic information about the location of the established refugee camps was requested from large amount of interests, raging from relief organisations to the media, the whole region was more or less constantly covered by clouds rendering it close to impossible to obtain useful data for almost a month. An ERS SAR scene was acquired on May 31. This scene should cover a total of 12 camps, including the 7 camps around Kukes in Albania. In addition we obtained one ERS SAR scene acquired on August 4 1997 and one on August 9 1999, to investigate the camp areas before the camps were established and after they had been abandoned. Precipitation data obtained for the five days preceding each acquisition show close to zero rainfall for the two acquisitions in 1999 and only small amounts for the acquisition in 1997, which should give very similar situations regarding the soil moisture. The region covered in the images is very hilly, and includes a.o. a large mountain massif separating Albania from Kosovo and Macedonia. The Albanian region is dominated by mining industry, and contains mainly forest and more or less abandoned agricultural fields in addition to some villages and smaller settlements. The part of Macedonia covered in the images constitutes mainly of a very large agricultural area in addition to several villages and settlements of various sizes. Unfortunately, we did not have any high-resolution DTM-data for the region, and as a consequence we had big difficulties trying to geo-rectify the ERS images. The IRS-1 D image was used for selecting ground control points. In the end we were only able to rectify the part of the images covering the Kukes village in Albania to a level where the refugee camps could be recognised, mostly due to a large river passing through this region. In the part of the images covering Macedonia there is not enough distinct features around each camp that can be used for a similar rectification. Rectifying the whole image using points equally distributed around in the image did not reveal any distinct indications of the refugee camps in the area where they were supposed to be, even if the RMS-error of the ground control points were low. Thus our analysis had to be concentrated around the 7 small camps lying close to the Kukes village in Albania.

From Figure 4.24 we see that 4-5 out of 7 camps could easily be detected in the ERS SAR image. Camp 4 and 7 is located within the village area and can thus not be separated from the already existing settlement, neither in the SAR nor the optical image. Camp 1 could to some extent be recognised, though it is doubtful that this could have been done without guidance from the superimposed camp borders. These borders were provided by UNHCR staff which drew them on top of an earlier version of the optical image shown in Figure 4.3. In fact, using this optical image we were only able to identify camp 3,5 and 6 ourselves. The problem is of course that at this scale there is no distinct difference in the appearance of refugee settlements from other settlements, and the identification become especially difficult in an area as urbanised as this. Note that the airline field appears very clearly in the SAR image, black due to the level surface, which

Figure 4.25 shows the four biggest camps in this region at a larger scale. It is interesting to see that in the optical image to the right camp 6 is easiest to detect, while in the ERS SAR image to the left the extent of this camp is very difficult to determine. On the other hand, in the SAR image especially camp 5 appears very clearly, while in the optical image the extent of this camp is more difficult to determine. Thus to some extent, complementary information can be gained with combined use of both optical and radar sensors.

Figure 4.24. *Left) Excerpt of the ERS SAR image of May 31 1999 superimposed the borders of refugee camps in the Kukes region, Albania Right) The same area mapped by the IRS-1D satellite on May 27 1999 (colours added from the LANDSAT image of Sep. 1997).*

Figure 4.25. Zoomed view of the images shown in Figure 4.24.

Figure 4.26. To the left is shown an ERS SAR scene of the Kukes region from August 4 1997, before the establishment of the refugee camps. In the middle is shown the image of May 31 1999 when all camps had been established. To the right is a scene of August 9 1999 when all camps in the region had been abandoned.

Figure 4.26 shows to the left the region of interest before the camps were established, then in the middle the region when the camps had been established, and to the right the situation after all camps had been abandoned. We especially observe that the signatures is very similar within the superimposed camp extension on the before and after images, which also means that the material used for establishing the camps, such as tents has been removed. No distinct changes in the area can be observed, which also is expected taking into account the rather short period the situation lasted (less than half a year).

4.7 USE OF ERS SAR INTERFEROMETRY FOR PRODUCING AN ELEVATION MODEL

Attempts at producing a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) for Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia border region has been done using ERS SAR interferometry. SAR images from the ERS-1/2 tandem period (1-day interval between subsequent coverage) were used as input data. The software used is an ERDAS module named IFSAR.

Infocarto has delivered 5 DEMs covering the requested area. The final images were produced in ERDAS .img format with a pixel-size of 25m. The five DEMs obtained were not mosaicked due to the differences in heights for their overlapping areas, i.e. no overall DEM accurate enough to be used could be made. Large difference in the overlapping areas also means that the unreliability of the five independent scenes is too high for practical use, and the results will not be shown in order not to cause confusion.

Limitations of the method and dataset used:

- Interferometry is not a good technique for forest and densely sloped areas such as Kosovo. It is difficult to obtain a good correlation between input images for these kinds of areas.
- Good ground control points are very difficult to determine and position.
- It is of great importance with a very accurate calculation of the baseline between the two scenes used (i.e. to determine the difference between the two orbits used).
- Use of the first version of a software module that might not have been sufficiently validated for sloped areas.

Methods to obtain a better result for this area:

- Traditional DEMS obtained by using photogrammetric techniques, e.g. by using aerial photographs or SPOT stereopairs.
- The technique we have used (Interferometry) would require dedicated software whose results had been successfully proven. This would mean different software than the ERDAS IFSAR module for which only a first version has been released.

5 SOUTH-EASTERN NEPAL

5.1 BACKGROUND

In the Jhapa and Morang districts in the eastern Nepal there is five refugee camps hosting some 90,000 Bhutanese refugees. Compared to traditional refugee camp settlements Beldangi I-III, Goldhap, Khudunabari, Timai and Sarishare are all rather small, which has been conscious policy of the Nepalese government in order reduce the potential for conflicts between the refugees and locals and to minimise conflicts related to the exploitation of natural resources. The major influx of these refugees occurred from 1990 to 1993, and all camps still exist today. In the area more than 70% of the total land area has been cultivated, and the remaining forest resources occupy 10% and 16% of the land area of respectively Jhapa and Morang. Deforestation is considered the most serious threat arising from the presence of the refugees, the population influx adding to the existing pressure on the local forest resources, though no formal study on the impacts of refugee firewood gathering has ever been carried out [UNHCR, 1998]. In some cases the camp areas had already suffered from previous human interference and were already in degraded or bare condition, though further impacts arose from the camp establishment due to e.g. clearing of unstable trees and ground level vegetation for building houses at safe locations [UNHCR, 1998]. Some of the camps are threaten by seasonal flooding.

The satellite data set for this area includes a LANDSAT-7 ETM+ scene of November 6 1999, two SPOT XS scenes of respectively February 16 1989 and January 5 1992, two ERS SAR scenes of respectively June 21 1992 and May 15 1996, and one IKONOS scene from May 2000 (Pan+MS). In addition we have received topographic paper-maps covering all refugee settlements at a scale of 1:25,000, made by the Survey Dep. of Nepal. These maps are based on aerial photographs acquired in 1992, and were verified in the field in 1996.

More information about the refugee situation in Nepal can e.g. be found at:
<http://www.unhcr.ch/world/asia/nepal.htm>

5.2 USE OF LANDSAT7 ETM+

The *Overview* and *Camp location and surroundings* maps are based on the LANDSAT7 ETM+ image. The spatial resolution of the image was enhanced using a RGB→IHS→RGB transformation available in the ERmapper software package.

The north-south distribution of the camps is very narrow compared to the east-west direction. We thus found it most sufficient to make two overview maps in order to have a sufficient size of the maps and to emphasis the important information. Most of the vector data in the maps was revealed through in-depth analysis of the LANDSAT-image, especially the 15m resolution panchromatic band contains much information about linear features. Also the two SPOT scenes were valuable for deriving this information. On the other hand using only the satellite images it is not possible to obtain any information about the type and width of e.g. the roads, also parts of the roads may 'disappear' due forest cover or low contrast against the surroundings. The image analysis was later verified using the topographic maps at scale 1:25,000. These maps do to some extent include information about the width of the various roads. In addition to the roads leading to the various refugee camps we have only included what we believe is the major roads in the region. The two *Overview* maps are showed in Figure 5.2 and Figure 5.3, and the *Camp location and surroundings* maps are shown in Figure 5.4 to Figure 5.8.

The *Camp location and surroundings* maps have been made using the LANDSAT7 ETM+ image, and processed in the same way as was done for the Overview maps. Each map covers about 10*10km. These maps are presented in Figure 5.4 to Figure 5.8.

Figure 5.1. Localisation of the satellite data obtained for the Nepal case study area.

5.2.1 OVERVIEW MAP

Morang and western Jhapa districts, Nepal
Overview: Infrastructure and water resources

Figure 5.2. Overview map for the Sanischare and Beldangi refugee camp settlements in Nepal.

5.2.2 CAMP LOCATION AND SURROUNDINGS

The Sanischare refugee settlement, Nepal
 Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure and water resources

Figure 5.4. The Sanischare refugee camp in Nepal.

The Beldangi refugee settlements, Nepal Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure and water resources

Figure 5.5. The Beldangi refugee camp settlements in Nepal

The Khudunabari refugee settlement, Nepal
Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure and water resources

Figure 5.6. The Khudunabari refugee camp in Nepal.

The Timai refugee settlement, Nepal
Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure and water resources

Figure 5.7. The Timai refugee camp in Nepal

The Goldhap refugee settlement, Nepal
 Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure and water resources

Figure 5.8. The Goldhap refugee camp in Nepal.

5.3 USE OF IKONOS

The *Camp Overview* and *Detailed Infrastructure* map is made from the IKONOS scenes acquired during May 1999, and is prepared in the scale of 1:10,000. It shows the camp and the major roads leading to the camp. It also shows all other extracted features in the camp, except the camp huts. The different infrastructure buildings are coloured by category, according to the legend. The surrounding civilian villages are labelled with their names.

The corner co-ordinates provided by the data-provider Space Imaging were used for the initial orientation of the image. The rectification was further improved using a map at scale 1:25,000. The mapping was performed by interpretation and onscreen digitising of the two different images produced (RGB image and NIR+RG image).

Many objects interpreted in the images are possible to identify with help of existing maps, but mainly objects outside the camp. Inside the camps there is a need for additional data about the infrastructure. However it is easy to extract objects such as buildings from the satellite images. It is impossible to see if the buildings are schools or medical centres etc. Information from people working in the camp is important for the final result and also for acceptance of the product.

Some features in Nepal, for example the police office, were located with the satellite image and identified with the map. Other infrastructure buildings were located with the satellite image and identified with information from local relief staff. To extract the camp huts both images were needed, to see which dots were huts and which were trees.

The detailed camp infrastructure map is made from the IKONOS scene and prepared for printing at a scale of 1:5,000. It shows all minor roads within the camp, the infrastructure buildings in different colours depending on category and a dot for each camp hut. By using the dots, all camp huts are counted for each camp.

The visual interpretation of the number of huts in the Beldangi refugee camps fits quit well with figures reported by the UNHCR-office in Kathmandu. From the image it was interpreted to be 44,100 huts while the official number is 44,556, i.e. the error is about only 1%. The difference in area can be due to the rules for measuring the camp size. In the interpretation the boundaries were set by the edge of the wood. From the image analysis the camp area was measured to be 125.5 ha, while the official area is 116.6 ha. This difference is mainly due to an unclear definition of the borders of the camp.

5.3.1 CAMP OVERVIEW

Beldangi, Nepal

Camp overview - infrastructure

Overview

Legend

- ▲ cemetery
- Health facilities
- petrol pump
- police station
- school
- ▲ major roads
- ▲ paths
- ▲ river
- ▲ small roads
- ▲ stream
- camp border
- cemetery
- civil village
- ferro cement tanks
- health facilities
- large houses
- mechanical workshop
- offices/centers
- police station
- refugees women forum
- relief items distribution centers
- relief items storage centers
- river area
- school
- water collection sites
- water tower
- Agriculture area
- Agriculture area
- Forest
- Bushes
- Grass
- Camp huts
- Infrastructure
- Terracing
- Paths
- Small roads
- Major roads
- River
- River area
- Stream
- Water tower
- Clouds

Beldangi camps - Nepal	
Camp 1	Area: 418,732m ² , Population: 15,000
Camp 2	Area: 500,800m ² , Population: 18,000
Camp 2 elevation:	Area: 337,200m ² , Population: 10,250
Date:	NOV-04
Projection:	UTM, zone 45
Origin:	87E / 26N
Scale factor:	0.9994
Data source:	NOV-05 2, 10p-16-10-0 Space Imaging 20, 30
© 2004-2005 maps © The Survey Dept. of Nepal 1996	Map produced by Srinivas 2005
ENVIREFA	NERFC Srinivas Indira UMACI

Figure 5.9. Camp overview map for the Beldangi refugee camp settlements.

5.3.2 DETAILED CAMP INFRASTRUCTURE

Beldangi, Nepal

Detailed Camp Infrastructure

Overview

Legend

- Beldangi 1
- Beldangi 2
- Beldangi 3
- ▲ secondary
- Health facilities
- petrol pump
- △ police station
- school
- ▲ major roads
- ▲ minor roads
- ▲ small roads
- ▲ stream
- ▲ river
- ▲ water tower
- ▲ water collection sites
- ▲ water tower
- ▲ camp boundary
- ▲ secondary
- ▲ chul village
- ▲ three constant tanks
- ▲ health facilities
- ▲ large houses
- ▲ school/workshop
- ▲ office/warehouse
- ▲ petrol station
- ▲ refugee women centre
- ▲ relief items distribution centre
- ▲ relief items storage centre
- ▲ river area
- ▲ school
- ▲ water collection sites
- ▲ water tower

- Agriculture area
- Bushes
- Forest
- Grass
- Camp huts
- Infrastructure
- Major roads
- Small roads
- Paths
- Stream
- Water tower
- River
- River area

0 200 400 600 Meters

0 0.2 Miles

Beldangi camps - Nepal	
Camp 1:	Area: 818,300m ² , Population: 15,000
Camp 2:	Area: 300,000m ² , Population: 18,900
Camp 2 extension:	Area: 307,200m ² , Population: 10,250
Datum:	WGS-84
Projection:	UTM zone 45
Origin:	97E, 0N
Scale factor:	0.9981
Data source:	INCHS & Map 1:250000 Series (Imagery 2001)
Topographic maps:	© The Survey Dept. of Nepal 1996
Map produced by:	ENVIREF
	MINGO SARVA HINDIA UNION

Figure 5.10. Detailed camp infrastructure map for the Beldangi camp settlements in Nepal.

Beldangi, Nepal

Detailed Camp Infrastructure

Figure 5.11. Detailed Camp infrastructure map for the Beldangi II and Ext.

5.4 WATER RESOURCE MAPPING

5.4.1 BACKGROUND

Nepal is a country rich in freshwater resources, these resources, however, are unevenly distributed and remain undeveloped. In rural Nepal, vast numbers of people lack access to safe drinking water and rudimentary sanitation surfaces. Currently, only 34% of the population have access to safe water and only 3% to sanitary facilities. Lack of access to water also creates a tremendous burden on women's time and energy, as they must spend many hours each day collecting sufficient water for drinking and cooking. Thus the problem of drinking water is one of both quality and quantity.

The water resources study covered only mapping of surface waters (i.e. rivers and lakes) by using satellite imagery. The area under investigation includes the Morang and Jhapa districts, where all the refugee camps are located.

5.4.2 DATA AND METHODS

The data used are two SPOT XS images acquired respectively on February 16 1989 and January 5 1992, and a LANDSAT ETM+ image acquired on November 6 1999. The two SPOT images were used for mapping the surface water resources, i.e. mainly rivers. The LANDSAT image was used together with the SPOT image of January 5 1992 for studying changes in the river channels due to erosion and flooding.

The image bands used for highlighting the surface water and the sand cover were band two (0.61 to 0.68 μm , i.e. red) in the red channel, a combination of band one (.50 to 0.59 μm , i.e. green) and band three (0.79 to 0.89 μm , i.e. near infrared) in the green channel and band one for the blue channel. The surface waters (rivers) were mapped using simple image enhancement techniques highlighting the linear features and on-screen digitising. The result of the surface water analysis is presented in Figure 5.2 and Figure 5.3.

The last task in this area was studying the change in watercourse channels due to erosion, which was done by comparing the watercourses digitised from the SPOT images of respectively 1989 and 1992 and the LANDSAT-7 image from 1999. All the rivers are originated in the high mountains in the north and they flow southward. There is a variation in the discharge of the rivers between the different seasons; this can be recognised by the fact that, the river during flooding period develops wide channels (sand cover in the images). The velocity of the water is high at the foot of the mountain area, for this reason the channels are straighter than down stream where the rivers are meandering and develop oxbow in some places. Groundwater has high chances to develop down stream in the plain area where the slope is gentle give chances for infiltration, specially areas where the rivers are meandering and the oxbow developed. All the camps are located in the north part in forestry area beside the rivers.

Conclusion

The area is rich in freshwater resources, these resources, however, are unevenly distributed and remain undeveloped, for detail studies more time is needed and more data. Water resource pollution can be a problem, which need more investigation and different data sources.

Change in Water Courses From 1992 to 1999

Legend

- Water course 1999
- Water course in 1992
- Town
- Refugee Camps

Changes in water courses for the Western Jhapa region	
Date: 2000	Map produced by: NERDC 2000
Projection: UTM	Scale: 1:50,000
Data source: UNEP & UNHCR/NERDC	NERDC
Map scale: 1:50,000	UNEP
Map scale: 1:50,000	UNHCR
Map scale: 1:50,000	UNEP/NERDC

Figure 5.12. Changes in the water courses in the Western Jhapa region from 1992 to 1999.

5.5 VEGETATION COVER MAPPING

The vegetation cover mapping is based on supervised classification of band 1-7 (excluding band 6) of the LANDSAT ETM+ image. Training data was selected using topographic maps at scale 1:25,000 and visual interpretation of the image. The topographic maps include little vegetation and natural resource information (i.e. the topography and infrastructure is the most important information in the map). For this reason only a limited number of classes could be selected and separated, including settlement, cultivation, riverbanks (sand), vegetation of unknown type, and the three different forest classes Sisau, mixed broad-leaved, and dense mixed (mainly Säl). The maximum likelihood classification algorithm was used, together with a neighbour filter in order to smooth out small areas, resulting in a minimum area of 150*150m for a given class. Although quite general, the classification results agreed fairly well with the topographic maps, while the real value/meaning of especially the cultivation class is rather diffuse, but it is believed to be mainly rain-dependent agricultural fields. Given the background information we this is the best result that can be achieved. The result for Morang and western Jhapa districts are shown in Figure 5.13.

Figure 5.13. Vegetation cover for the Morang and western Jhapa district, Nepal.

5.6 USE OF ERS SAR

Two ERS SAR scenes obtained respectively on June 21, 1992 and May 15, 1996 cover the four refugee settlements located in the Jhapa district. After careful geo-rectification using topographic maps at 1:25,000 and the Landsat-7 ETM+ scene the location and extent of the various refugee settlements were sought in the images. This was done using vector data derived from the topographic maps made in 1992 (revised in 1996) and the Landsat-7 ETM+ image. Due that the area is rather flat an acceptable geo-rectification of the images was reached even without using DTM-data. The SAR images have been superimposed roads, rivers and camp borders, all derived from the Landsat-7 ETM+ image and the available topographic maps. In the Landsat-7 image all camps appear very clear compared to their surroundings, having a brownish colour tone. Unfortunately, no information about the precipitation before and during the acquisitions has been obtained, but it is reasonable to believe that the atmospheric conditions might be different as the monsoon season in this region starts in June. Thus care should be taken when e.g. performing change detection analysis. Figure 5.14 to Figure 5.17 shows the four refugee settlements that have been analysed. To the left in the figures is the ERS SAR image acquired on June 21, 1992, in the middle the ERS SAR image acquired on May-15, 1996 and to the right a 15m-sharpened RGB-combination of the Landsat-7 ETM+ scene acquired on November 6, 1999.

The eastern part of the Beldangi refugee camp settlements shown in Figure 5.14 was opened in May 1992, about a month before the first ERS SAR image was acquired. In this image indications of man-made features are clearly evident as bright spots within the camp area, and for larger parts of the camp there is a good contrast to the surrounding forestry area. On the other hand, we see that the area covered by bright spots is smaller than the superimposed border of the camp as derived from the topographic map. The remaining parts of the Beldangi camps were opened in June 1992 (and further increased in November 1992), but in the ERS SAR image from 1992 only the camp opened in May can be identified. The image might have been acquired prior to this establishment, as we do not know how accurate the reported openings of the various camps are, and what state a camp is at when reported open. Looking at the image from 1996 the western camp is displayed very well, just as good as in the optical image, at there is a perfect fit with the superimposed camp border derived from the topographic map, thus the perimeter could easily be measured. The eastern camp appears quite similar in the two images, which support the suggestion that the western camp still wasn't opened when the first image was acquired.

The Khudunabari refugee camp settlement shown in Figure 5.15 was opened in March 1993, and as can be seen in the first image there is no evidence of man-made features within the superimposed camp area. Results from analysis of a SPOT XS scene obtained in 1989 suggest that a forest cover the camp area at this stage. In the image from 1996 the camp area is easily detectable and it appears even better than in the optical Landsat image. The small mismatch with the superimposed camp border is due to errors arising from the geo-rectification. From this image the perimeter of the camp could easily be measured.

The Timai refugee camp settlement shown in Figure 5.16 was opened in November 1991. In the SAR image from 1992 there are indications of man-made features within the superimposed camp border, but the contrast to the surroundings is low. For this area the geo-rectification was not as accurate as it should be for a distinct localisation of the camp, and we are unsure whether the camp area has been superimposed in its right position. In addition, the camp area is surrounded by other settlements, which further complicates the determination of the localisation and extension of the camp. In the image from 1996 there is also evidences of

man-made features, but the bright spots appear at other places within the superimposed camp area than in the image from 1992. It is doubtful that this camp could have been identified without using the superimposed camp border as guide.

The Goldhap refugee settlement shown in Figure 5.17 was opened in June 1992, but no indications about man-made features can be seen in the ERS SAR image from June 21 1992. In the image from 1996 the camp is evident though, even if the contrast against the surroundings is smaller than what has been observed for the Beldangi and Khudunabari camps. Although also this camp is surrounded by forest on three sides, this forest is of another type and is denser than for the Beldangi case. Goldhap is surrounded by other settlements on the western side, which might explain the ambiguous border in that direction.

In summary, we observe that for the first two cases presented the refugee settlements can be identified very accurately, including their extension, as the residences within the camp areas appear with a very bright signature against a darker background. In the two next cases the localisation of the camp areas is more ambiguous, and for the Timai cases we are not even sure whether we have been able to localise the actual camp area at all. There might be several explanations for the varied results. Firstly, we observe that the contrast against the surroundings is very important for the identification of the camp settlement. The Beldangi camps and the Goldhap camp is both surrounded by forest, though of different type and density, which might explain parts of the differences. The two other camps lie in a cultivated area, and both are surrounded by other settlements, still Khudunabari is easily detectable while the Timai camp is not. Unfortunately, we do not know what type of constructions has been used in the various camps, but the distinct differences might indicate that different materials (at least for the roofs) has been used for the residences and buildings within the various camps. The Beldangi and Khudunabari camps are oriented in an almost north-south direction while the two other camps is oriented in more northwest-southeastwards direction, which also might explain parts of the differences. A third explanation might be different degree and type of vegetation with the various camps.

Figure 5.14. The Beldangi refugee settlements in Nepal imaged respectively in 1992, 1996 and 1999 (from left to right).

Figure 5.16. The Timai refugee settlement in Nepal imaged respectively in 1992, 1996 and 1999 (from left to right).

Goldhap refugee camp area 06-Nov-1999

Figure 5.17. The Goldhap refugee settlement in Nepal imaged respectively in 1992, 1996 and 1999 (from left to right).

5.7 CHANGE DETECTION USING SPOT XS AND LANDSAT ETM+

No field observations are available for this study thus only quantitatively remarks can be made for the observed changes. It should also be emphasised that satellite image analysis alone is not enough to make any assumptions whether the observed changes are due to the presence of the refugee settlements. On the other hand, the satellite image analysis can be used to prove that changes occurred even before some of the camps were established.

Sanischare camp area

The camp was officially opened in May 1992.

Comparing the two images of respectively January 1992 (SPOT) and November 1999 (LANDSAT) shown in Figure 5.18 it seems like the whole region has been brought under cultivation sometime during this time interval. At the same time it is difficult to determine the exact location of the Sanischare camp in the image, as it does not show any clear contrast against its surroundings. Estimated from the images the total forest-covered area is reduced from 1.4km² in 1992 to only 0.3km² in 1999.

Beldangi camp area

These camps were officially opened between May (eastern part, Beldangi I) and November 1992 (western part, Beldangi II+Ext.).

Between the satellite image acquisitions of January 1992 (SPOT) and November 1999 (LANDSAT-7) the total forest-covered area around the camps has been reduced from 5.9km² to 5km², which basically is the area covered by the Beldangi II+Ext (Figure 5.19). At the same time the western part of the forest appears much denser in the 1992-image compared to the 1999-image, which may imply harvesting also here.

Khudunadari camp area

This camp was officially opened in March 1993.

In the SPOT-image from February 1989 the camp area is covered by a forest some 0.8km², which is completely removed in the 1999 LANDSAT-7 image (Figure 5.20). Without further information it is not possible to say whether this removal is due to the presence of the refugee camp.

Timai camp area

This camp was officially opened in November 1991, but not sufficiently covered in the SPOT-image of February 1989, thus no analysis can be performed.

Goldhap camp area

This camp was officially opened in June 1992.

The SPOT-image from February 1989 shows that there are several clear-cut areas in the region where the camp has been established, including at the future location of the camp (Figure 5.21). The LANDSAT-7 image of November 1999 shows no significant changes in the forest cover in the region from the 1989-situation.

Sanischare refugee camp area 05-Jan-1992

Sanischare refugee camp area 06-Nov-1999

Figure 5.18. The Sanischare camp area mapped respectively on Jan-05-1992 (left) and Nov-06-1999 (right)

Figure 5.19. The Beldangi refugee settlements mapped respectively on Jan-05-1992 (left) and Nov-06-1999 (right).

Khudunabari refugee camp area 16-Feb-1989

Khudunabari refugee camp area 06-Nov-1999

Figure 5.20. The Khudunabari refugee camp mapped respectively on Feb-16-1989 (left) and Nov-05-1999 (right).

Figure 5.21. The Goldharp refugee camp mapped respectively on Feb-16-1989 (left) and Nov-05-1999 (right).

6 NORTH-EASTERN KENYA

In the North-eastern Kenya two refugee settlements have been analysed. The refugee camps in the Dadaab Refugee Camp Complex are located in three locations – Dagahaley, Ifo and Hagadera. Dadaab is located in the Garissa district, some 110-km east of the Garissa town in the northeastern province of Kenya. The Garissa district is an arid and semi-arid zone with a fragile ecosystem. The existing vegetation is shrubby savannah with a domination of the acacias. The agricultural potentials are extremely low, close non-existent. The average annual rainfall varies from 150 to 300mm. Potential evaporation annual average oscillates between 2,100 and 2,500mm. It is a hot to very hot zone, with an average annual temperature between 24 and 30°C. The maximum temperature lie between 30 and 36°C and the minimum between 18 and 24°C.

The three camps were established between 1991 and 1992. 95% of the refugees come from Somalia and the remainder comes from Ethiopia, Sudan and Uganda. The male-female ratio is roughly equal, with children making up 50% of the population. The local population has grown from 4,000 to 15,000. The local people congregate near the camps in order to trade with the refugees.

More information about the refugee situation in Kenya can e.g. be found at:

<http://www.unhcr.ch/world/afri/kenya.htm>

Camp	Physical Features				Human Features		
	Altitude (m)	Land Form	Vegetation	Camp Area (ha.)	Camp Population	Average Household Size	Density (person/ha.)
Ifo	100-200	Alluvial plain	dwarf and medium shrubby herbaceous savannah	290.9	24,900	3.3	86
Dagahaley	100-200	Alluvial flat plain	medium and dwarf shrubby savannah	235.5	38,250	5.6	162

Table 6.1. Summary of Camp Characteristics (Source UNHCR and ENVIREF).

For this study one IKONOS scene 11*11km wide covering Ifo and Dagahaley camps was obtained, see Figure 6.1. The scene includes both the panchromatic and multispectral bands, and was acquired on respectively May 26 and May 25, 2000. Two images, i.e. a merge of panchromatic and multi-spectral data, were made (as described in Chapter 3).

Even though GPS-measurements were available, these could not be used because of poor documentation, i.e. they were not visible in the images that was supposed to show their location. There is a need for educating the relief personnel on how to choose and document (text/drawings) good ground control points. Instead the satellite registered corner co-ordinates provided by Space Imaging were used. From experience the IKONOS provided corner co-ordinates have an absolute accuracy of about 10m.

No supporting information or maps were available for evaluating the interpretation. The features extracted were major and minor roads, paths, rivers, river area, streams, camp huts, infrastructure, buildings, ferro-cement tanks, fences, camp borders and civil villages. To extract the camp huts both images were needed, to see which dots were huts and which were

Dagahaley, Kenya

Camp overview -infrastructure

Overview

Legend

- Major roads
Minor roads
- Blocks
- Camp border fence
- Green belt areas
- Infrastructure areas
- Infrastructure fence village
- Block
- Infrastructure
- Civil village
- Major road
- Minor road
- Green belt
- Pasture
- Shrub on elevated plain
- Shrub on steep forest plain
- Cloud
- Cloud shadow

Dagahaley camp, Kenya	
Area: 3,970,000 m ² Estimated population: 38,250	
Datum: WGS 84 Projection: UTM, zone 37 Origin: 40°E / 0°N Scale factor: 0.9996	Map produced by: Gazika 2000
Data source: BIOSIS 2, Map 28-3200 © Spaw Irregnc 2000	

Figure 6.2. Overview map for the Dagahaley camp in Kenya

Ifo, Kenya

Camp overview -infrastructure

Overview

Legend

- Major roads
- Minor roads
- Blocks
- Camp border
- Green built areas
- Infrastructure areas
- Village
- Block
- Infrastructure
- Civil village
- Major road
- Minor road
- Green built
- Pasture
- Shrub on elevated plain
- Shrub on lower flood plain
- Closed
- Closed shrubland

Ifo camp, Kenya	
Area: 4 170,000 m ² Estimated pop. 24,800	
Data by: WGS-84	Map produced by: Satebita 2000
Projection: UTM, zone 37	
Origin: 40 E 0 N	
Scale: 1:5000	
Units: Meters	
Map source: MONOS L, Mar 20 2000 © Space Imaging 2000	

Figure 6.3. Overview map for the Ifo camp in Kenya.

Dagahaley, Kenya

Detailed Camp Infrastructure

Overview

Legend

- Major roads
- Minor roads
- Cattle
- Pasture
- Brush on alluvial plain
- Brush on river flood plain
- Cloud
- Cloud shadow

- Block
- Infrastructure
- Civil village
- Major road
- Minor road
- Clean soil
- Pasture
- Brush on alluvial plain
- Brush on river flood plain
- Cloud
- Cloud shadow

Dagahaley camp, Kenya		
Area: 3,270,000 m ² Estimated population: 38,250		
Datum: WGS 84 Projection: UTM, zone 37 Origin: 48°E, 0°N Spheroid: GRS80	Map produced by: Satella 2000	
Data source: INDOSS II Nov-20-2000 © Space Imaging 2000		ME/NSC E/MS/4 W/MS/1 U/MS/1

Figure 6.4. Detailed camp infrastructure map for the Dagahaley refugee camp in Kenya.

Ifo, Kenya

Detailed Camp Infrastructure

Overview

Legend

- Camp built
- Camp boundary
- Major roads
- Minor roads
- Shrub
- Camp fence
- Pasture
- Green field areas
- Infrastructure areas
- Infrastructure fences
- Village

- Shrub
- Infrastructure
- Civil village
- Major road
- Minor road
- Green field
- Pasture
- Shrub on elevated plain
- Shrub on river flood plain
- Cloud
- Cloud shadow

Ifo camp, Kenya	
Area: 4,170,000 m ² ; Estimated population: 24,600	
Datum: WGS-84 Projection: UTM zone 37 Origin: 40 E / 0°N Scale factor: 0.9996	Map produced by: Satelus 2000
Data source: IKONOS 2, May-26-2000 © Space Imaging 2000	

Figure 6.5. Detailed camp infrastructure map for the Ifo camp in Kenya.

7 CONCLUSION

Use of satellite images to support management of refugee camps is an innovative approach. The relief agencies, which are the main target group for the ENVIREF study, have little or no experience with use of satellite images in their decision-making procedures, and currently there are no budgets dedicated for obtaining such data. Personnel working in the field generally do not have any experience with this technology, and can have difficulties interpreting the images in order to get the needed information. For this reason it is not obvious to them that the use of satellite data could be beneficial, both technically and economically. It thus been our challenge in the project to demonstrate that satellite imagery can be a valuable information source for fulfilling certain geographic information needs, especially when existing maps are out of date, unreliable or difficult to obtain.

During the ENVIREF project we have already documented that there is an increasing demand for geographic information in humanitarian relief operations, and that often the time frame is the most critical factor for obtaining the required information [Enviref, 1999]. Defined from the first user workshop the most important information requirement and acceptable delivery time were:

- Infrastructure overview, including travelling distances, type and status of the major access roads, and land-use for camp site selection and logistics, 1-14 days
- Land-ownership, 1-7 days
- Water resources (ground water, lakes, rivers, indicators of water resources), 1-2 weeks
- Co-ordination maps (which organisations are involved and where), 1 week
- Landmines, 2-3 weeks
- Camp infrastructure, 3-4 weeks
- Agriculture (development, extent, soil, crops and livestock, refugee vs. local farming), 1-2 months
- Environmental aspects such as forest, tree species and deforestation, vegetation species, soil, quality of bio-mass, and water pollution, 2-12 months

It is important to note that all this information cannot be derived from satellite imagery, e.g. land-ownership, landmines, and water pollution. But, use of satellite data can contribute to fast, cost-efficient and objective information on many parameters in the above list, especially in areas where existing maps are of low quality or difficult to obtain. Technically, there is a contradiction between large spatial coverage and high spatial resolution. Therefore use of several types of satellite sensors in combination are needed for obtaining the required information at appropriate mapping scales. This means that satellite sensors with spatial resolution from 10-30m such as LANDSAT and SPOT, are useful for mapping the camp area surroundings, i.e. at scales of 1:20,000 and lower. For detailed mapping at scale 1:10,000 and higher of e.g. tents, buildings and infrastructure it is necessary to use very-high spatial resolution satellites such as IKONOS.

In rural and semi-rural areas some kind of *a priori* knowledge of the location of the refugee camps is needed for limiting the search area, and for avoiding confusion with other kinds of settlements. Further, a number of ground control points is needed for accurate ge-positioning of the satellite images, but these must be better documented than in the reports that has been available for us during the project.

Medium resolution (5-30m) satellite remote sensing images can provide much of the information needed by the relief agencies, but not always within the required time frame. To get a thematic overview of a region, e.g. major infrastructure, brief vegetation cover and potential water resources, images a few years old can often be used. Given the mission goal of the LANDSAT-7 programme to acquire and periodically update a global archive of daytime, substantially cloud-free images of all land areas of the world, this sensor could become a particular valuable data source for the relief community in the coming years. Depending on the data-distributor one must allow up to 10 days for receiving archive images. We suggest buying data directly through the USGS internet-server, where the requested image can be obtained within 24hours using ftp.

The delivery time for new image acquisitions depends among others on the where the region of interest is compared to the satellite orbit, the weather conditions (i.e. mostly the cloud coverage), other acquisition-orders, etc. Everything from a few days to a few months must be expected. Satellites with rotating viewing capacity of the sensor will potentially have a shorter re-visiting frequency.

In addition to knowing where the refugee camps are located, estimating the number of refugees allocated in a camp is especially important. A theoretical relation between the land area covered and the population rate for more or less planned urban settlements can be established, and attempts to determine such a relation also for refugee settlements using very high resolution optical imagery has been done by Bjørge [1999]. For refugee settlements more complex factors complicate the relationship compared to urban settlements, in addition it is difficult to obtain enough statistically significant material to make a good model. As we have shown the extent of a refugee camp settlement can in most cases be measured using both optical and SAR medium-resolution satellite images. Given more research about the mathematical relation between the area and population, medium-resolution satellite imagery could be a valuable information source for the relief organisations when planning the amount of food and medicine needed.

Both LANDSAT and SPOT data have been used to map the surface water situation over a wider region. Combined with digital elevation data also the river flow direction is determined. Multi-temporal acquisitions by SPOT and LANDSAT over the same area in Nepal have been used to derive changes in the watercourse. Even though several changes were identified at the more level part of the region, no camps appeared to be in danger of flooding or erosion as a consequence changes in the watercourse.

Vegetation cover mapping using LANDSAT has been performed both with and without additional information about the vegetation situation in the investigated areas. Analysis performed without such information can only be used to make general assumptions about the vegetation cover, such as separating vegetated and non-vegetated regions, e.g. the location and distribution of forest (without mentioning the type of wood). These maps can on the other hand be prepared very quickly, and also be used to plan where in-depth field observations should be collected. Having access to some kind of information about the vegetation in an area, e.g. through field observations or existing vegetation maps, more detailed maps can be prepared, showing e.g. the location of the various forest and vegetation types appearing in the region. This was done for the vegetation cover study in the Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia region using forest classification maps from Albania.

Through the analysis we have shown that in most cases the location and extent of a refugee camp can be measured using ERS SAR imagery, once the contrast against its surroundings are high enough. But there are situations where the method fails, for instance in Macedonia where it was not possible to geo-locate the image with such accuracy that the various camps could be detected. Higher resolution radar imagery than is commercially available today is needed for performing analysis within the camp areas, e.g. such as counting the number of residences.

Under favourable conditions the number of tents present can be used to make rough estimates of the number of people residing within the camp area. During the Enviref project counting the number of tents and small houses inside the Beldangi refugee settlements in Nepal, and the Dagahaley and Ifo refugee settlements in Kenya has been done successfully using very-high resolution images from the IKONOS satellite. This number can then be used to estimate the approximate amount of affected people living in the camp. Thus, the use of very high-resolution satellite images may be a significant contribution towards better estimates of the number of people affected during the first stages of a crisis. We have also been able to delineate other important details within the camp, such as larger buildings hosting hospitals, schools, administration, police etc, in addition to water sites and wells, petrol pumps, and roads and footpaths of various size. IKONOS images also have the potential to be used for detailed refugee camp planning and assessments of environmental changes.

The most important aspect of the IKONOS data is the possibility to accurately reveal small details only a few meters wide in areas restricted from aerial surveys. The high spatial resolution makes it possible to perform detailed interpretation of e.g. infrastructure and settlements without use of field observations. The high spatial accuracy of the localisation of the image makes it possible to verify and eventually correct to position of features reported in the field.

Strategy and recommendation for future use, based on the data analysis in WP3000:

Satellite	Parameters ¹	Benefits	Limitations
LANDSAT TM	Vegetation cover, surface water	Large spatial coverage, high spectral resolution (7 bands), large archive	Low spatial resolution, expensive data
LANDSAT ETM+	Vegetation cover, surface water, infrastructure, camp location, settlements	Large spatial coverage, high spectral coverage (7 bands), panchromatic band (15m resolution), low data price (USD600), large archive	Low spatial resolution beside the panchromatic band
SPOT XS	Vegetation cover, surface water, infrastructure, camp location, settlements	High spatial resolution, medium spatial coverage	Low spectral resolution, expensive data, expensive data
IRS-1D	Surface water, infrastructure, camp location, settlements	Medium to high spatial resolution	Low radiometric resolution (low contrast)
ERS SAR	Camp location, settlements, digital elevation data	Operates independent of clouds and light, quite low data price	Difficult to interpret
IKONOS	Vegetation cover, surface water, infrastructure, residences	Very high spatial resolution, medium high spectral resolution	Small spatial coverage, expensive data

¹Without additional data such as e.g. existing maps or field observations only brief descriptions can be made regarding the vegetation cover

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